

**ASSESSMENT OF PLEURAL EFFUSION USING LIGHTS CRITERIA
AND ITS CORRELATION WITH ULTRASOUND THORAX AND ITS
IMPACT ON MANAGEMENT OF PLEURAL EFFUSION AND ITS
CORRELATION WITH PLEURAL FLUID PROCALCITONIN LEVELS**

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**In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
DOCTOR OF MEDICINE IN RESPIRATORY MEDICINE**

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATION	FULL FORM
PCT	Procalcitonin
USG	Ultrasonography
LDH	Lactate dehydrogenase
PA	Postero-anterior
AP	Anterior-posterior
BTS	British Thoracic Society
PLD	Posteriorchestwall lung base diameter
ng/ml	Nanograms per millilitre
pg/ml	Picograms per millilitre
FDG	Fluorodeoxyglucose
NT- ProBNP	N-terminal pro B-type natriuretic peptide
ADA	Adenosine deaminase
PPE	Parapneumonic effusion
PE	Pulmonary thromboembolic effusion
TPA	Tissue plasminogen activator
VATS	Video assisted thoracic surgery
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
IL	Interleukin
NO	Nitic oxide
FDA	Food drug administration
CRP	C-Reactive protein
ICD	Intercostal drainage
ROC	Receiver operator characteristic curve
ELISA	Enzyme linked immunoassay
%	Percentage
CKD	Chronic liver disease

CLD	Chronic kidney disease
HF	Heart failure
TB	Tuberculosis

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND:

Pleural effusion which is characterized by pathological accumulation of fluid in the pleural space, affects around 1.5 million people worldwide each year. There are numerous causes of pleural effusion, which when untreated or unidentified at an early stage, can lead to complications. Thoracic ultrasonography (USG) is a mobile, bedside, affordable, non- ionizing tool and not only helps in the identifying pleural effusion but also to distinguish between the different types of effusion. The ultrasound findings play a crucial role in guiding the decisions and ensure appropriate and effective treatment tailored to the specific characteristics of each effusion.

Procalcitonin (PCT) is a potential indicator of systemic inflammation due to infection. PCT has been investigated in this study to recognize its role in correlation with lights criteria and in the diagnosis of different etiologies of exudative and transudative pleural effusion, thereby enhancing clinical decision-making and optimizing patient management strategies.

There is a need for utilization of USG in every case of pleural effusion in regards to the patient's safety as well as for the decision of further management. This study emphasizes the need for ultrasound thorax to classify the type of pleural effusion, and correlating it with the Lights criteria and Procalcitonin levels to initiate appropriate management.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

The aim of the study is to determine the ultrasound thorax findings among the patients with pleural effusion and to correlate the Lights criteria with ultrasound thorax findings and pleural fluid procalcitonin levels and also to evaluate the impact of ultrasound thorax findings on the management of pleural effusion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross-sectional study on 89 patients with the diagnosis of pleural effusion, was carried out in the department of Respiratory Medicine OPD/ wards in BLDE[DU] Shri B M Patil medical college, Hospital and Research center, Vijayapura in this study. Ultrasound thorax and Diagnostic Pleural Fluid analysis was done in each patient, and Procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid was measured were measured by ELISA method.

RESULTS:

Among 89 patients enrolled in this study, the age of the patients being studied ranged from 18 years to 85 years & the mean age was 50.8 ± 18.1 years. In the transudative group, their ages were between 21 and 80 years with a mean \pm SD of 53.8 ± 14.2 years and in the exudative group their ages were between 18 and 85 years with a mean \pm SD of 49.3 ± 19.6 years. Male preponderance was seen in our study with 68.5%. Majority of the cases, 35 patients (39.33%) had complex septate finding in ultrasonography thorax followed by 32 patients (35.96%) with anechogenic finding, while 19 patients (21.35%) had complex non-septate finding, and 35 patients (39.33%) had complex septate finding and 3 (3.36%) patients had homogenous echoes finding. Among the complex septate pleural effusions in our study, thin septations were predominant 28 (80%) followed by thick septations which were 7 (20%) and 16 (17.9%) patients of exudative pleural effusions had thickened pleura which was statistically significant. Among the 89 cases, most of the pleural effusions were unilateral

(83.1%) and more common on right side (55 %). There was a positive and statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) correlation between anechogenic finding and complex septate finding on ultrasound with the type of pleural effusion defined by Light's criteria. Out of 89 pleural effusions in the gross category, the proportion of transudative cases is higher (50%), while in the moderate category, exudative cases are more prevalent (72.9%) with statistically significant correlation. Bilateral effusions are more common in transudative group (26.7%) compared to exudative group (11.9%). Most of the exudative effusions in our study were complex septated (39.3%), echogenic (3.3%) or complex non-septated (21.3%) on ultrasound with few being anechoic (35.9%). Transudative effusions were mostly anechoic (76.7%) in our study. Effusions without septations and loculations were mostly managed with therapeutic aspiration, while effusions with thin septations or loculations and with echoes were treated with ICD tube insertion and the cases with thick septations or multiple loculations were managed with surgical interventions like thoracotomy/VATS. The mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid in transudative pleural effusion group in this study was 0.32 ± 0.01 ng/ml and exudative pleural effusion was 9.67 ± 25.8 ng/ml with statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) value. Our study found that the mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid was significantly higher in Empyema group [49.2 ± 41.9 ng/ml] followed by parapneumonic effusion group [0.88 ± 0.95 ng/ml] compared to other groups, malignancy group [0.59 ± 0.21 ng/ml], Tuberculous group [0.50 ± 0.20 ng/ml] , Pulmonary Embolism group [0.34 ± 0.65 ng/ml] .The ROC analysis for an optimal discrimination between transudative and exudative effusion could be achieved at a cutoff point of 345.45pg/ml [0.345 ng/ml] with area under the curve of 0.989 [sensitivity:96.6% and specificity:96.8%]

CONCLUSION:

This study highlights the importance of ultrasound thorax as a valuable tool for the characterization of pleural effusion and guiding therapeutic interventions, ensuring precise and effective patient management. Complex septate finding and thickened pleura are high supportive of exudative effusions in our study while anechoic appearance of transudative effusions. Simple effusions without septations and loculations were mostly managed with therapeutic aspiration, while complex effusions, particularly those with thin septations or loculations, and with heterogenous or homogenous echoes often necessitated ICD tube insertion and those with thick septations or multiple loculations required more invasive procedures like thoracotomy/VATS. Measurement of procalcitonin in pleural fluid can be used to differentiate transudative from exudative pleural effusions and can also be used to differentiate empyema and parapneumonic effusions from other causes of exudative pleural effusions.

KEY WORDS: Ultrasonography, Lights criteria, Procalcitonin

INTRODUCTION

The pleural space is a potential space enclosed between the parietal and visceral layers of the pleura.¹ Pleural effusion is characterized by pathological accumulation of fluid in the pleural space.²

Pleural effusion affects around 1.5 million people worldwide each year.³ The occurrence indicates a pathological process, resulting from various factors that could originate primarily from the lungs or from another organ system, or may be the initial sign of a systemic disease.⁴ However, the etiology of pleural effusion is uncertain in approximately 20% of patients.²

To effectively treat pleural effusion, it is necessary to identify the underlying cause.² Determining whether the effusion is a transudate or an exudate is the initial step in evaluating pleural fluid, as it indicates the underlying pathophysiologic process, the differential diagnosis, and the necessity for additional investigations.^{5,6}

Light's criteria, which includes serum and pleural fluid biochemical studies, are routinely employed in clinical practice to differentiate between the exudative and transudative.⁷ Light's criteria combines three dichotomous tests to form a decision rule that is deemed positive if any of the tests are positive. It has a high sensitivity for

diagnosing exudative pleural effusions (98%), but its ability to exclude transudates is limited.⁸ This misclassification may subject patients to needless diagnostic tests and cause a delay in appropriate treatment.

The use of ultrasonography as a point-of-care test allows to detect pleural pathology accurately, while also ensuring safe access to the pleural space for thoracentesis or chest drain insertion.⁹ It identifies the pleural from parenchymal densities, in addition to determining the quantity, septations, echoes in the fluid, and pleural thickenings, which help in the patient's future therapy.¹⁰ It has also been stated in few studies that thoracic ultrasonography determines the type of effusion, the findings correlating with the transudative and exudative interpretations from the Light's criteria.¹¹

The type and nature of pleural effusion determine the mode of management - conventional or surgical approach. While major effusions require drainage to alleviate the patient's symptoms, treating the underlying cause can aid in the resolution of minimal pleural effusions.

Procalcitonin (PCT), a prohormone of calcitonin, is released physiologically by C-cells of thyroid gland.¹² A specific protease breaks down PCT into calcitonin, katalcalcin, and an N-terminal residue and its levels are undetectable in healthy individuals.¹³ Procalcitonin (PCT) synthesis is increased solely in reaction to bacterial infection, but not in response to non-infectious inflammation or nonbacterial infection and is emerging as a viable clinical indicator of bacterial infection.^{12,14} Higher procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid could suggest a more inflammatory or infectious etiology for the effusion, which is often associated with exudative pleural effusions.¹⁵

There is a need for utilization of USG in every case of pleural effusion in regards to the patient's safety as well as for the decision of further management. This study

emphasizes the need for ultrasound thorax to classify the type of pleural effusion, and correlating it with the Lights criteria and Procalcitonin levels to initiate appropriate management (conventional vs surgical).

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

AIM:

The aim of this study is to determine the need for ultrasound thorax to classify the type of pleural effusion, and correlation with the Lights criteria and Procalcitonin levels to initiate appropriate management.

OBJECTIVES:

1. Assessment of pleural effusion using ultrasound thorax
2. Correlating ultrasound thorax findings with pleural effusion lights criteria
3. Impact of ultrasound thorax findings on management of pleural effusion
4. To correlate pleural fluid procalcitonin levels with lights criteria.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HISTORY:

Imhotep, an Egyptian physician, was likely the first to describe pleural diseases in around 3000 BC. Although Hippocrates was more popularly credited with its recognition about 500 BC.¹⁶

A description of a water-seal chest drainage system was first given by Playfair in 1873 in the management of thoracic empyema.¹⁷

A German internist, Gotthard Bulau, in 1875, recommended closed water-seal chest drainage as an alternative to traditional rib excision and open tube drainage for treating empyema.¹⁸

In 1970, as a pulmonary fellow at Johns Hopkins Hospital, Dr. Light developed an interest in monitoring biochemical markers in pleural fluids to aid in the detection of effusions which was accepted by *Annals of Internal Medicine* in the year 1972.¹⁹

Cholesterol measurement as a diagnostic marker for distinction between transudative and exudative pleural effusion was first proposed in 1987 by Hamm et al.²⁰

Dr. Light pioneered pleural manometry in a therapeutic capacity to control pleural effusions. This involved using a U-shaped water manometer to observe pleural pressures during thoracentesis in 52 patients. The study concluded that it is safe to remove large amounts of pleural fluid (>1 L) as long as the pleural pressure did not drop below -20 cm H₂O.²¹

ANATOMY OF PLEURA²²

Two layers of serous membrane, called the parietal and visceral pleura, envelop each lung in the form of an invaginated, closed sac. The parietal pleura is divided into four divisions- cervical, diaphragmatic, mediastinal, costal. The cervical part (pleural dome) covers the inferior surface of the suprapleural membrane (in the region of the lung apex), the diaphragmatic part covers the superior (thoracic) surface of the respiratory diaphragm; and the mediastinal part covers the structures between the lungs and within the mediastinum forming the lateral border of the mediastinum and the costal (costovertebral) part lines the internal surface of the thoracic wall as well as the lateral aspects of the vertebral bodies and intervening intervertebral discs. The visceral pleura is the area that borders the tissues between the lobes and covers the surface of the lung. Around the base of the lung's root and pulmonary ligament, the visceral and parietal pleurae are connected with one another. During every stage of breathing, they are in close contact with one another but are able to freely slide due to presence of thin layer of serous fluid. The lung apices are covered by the pleura one inch above the medial third of the clavicle. The pleura extends below the lung 4 to 5 cm anteriorly and 9-10cm posteriorly at the lower aspect. They travel behind the sternoclavicular joints and meet at the lower border of the manubrium

sterni, the anterior margin is seen to converge. It is noticeable that the anterior boundary continues to align with the fourth costal cartilage level. The left pleura curves out and descends lateral to the sternum's border, halfway to the heart's apex, while the right pleura continues vertically. Each lateral turn occurs at the 6th costal cartilage and then continues around the chest wall, intersecting the midclavicular line at the 8th rib and the mid axillary line at the 10th rib. The lower border creates the costophrenic recess, stopping just shy of the costal margin. It intersects with the 12th rib at the lower border of the sacrospinalis muscle and extends horizontally to reach the lower border of the 12th thoracic vertebra.

FUNCTIONAL ANATOMY ²³

The pleura is observed to consist of five layers in light microscopy. The five layers are

1. Mesothelium
2. Submesothelial connective tissue
3. Layer of elastic tissue
4. Another layer of loose connective tissue which contains blood vessels, lymph vessels and nerves.
5. Deep fibroelastic layer adherent to the underlying tissue.

VASCULAR SUPPLY & LYMPHATIC DRAINAGE ²⁴

PARIETAL PLEURA:

The blood supply is abundant and is primarily provided by systemic blood vessels.

- Costal pleura by Intercostal and internal mammary arteries
- Cervical pleura by Subclavian artery
- Mediastinal pleura by Bronchial, internal thoracic, superior phrenic and mediastinal vessels

- Diaphragmatic pleura by Superior phrenic branch of internal mammary artery, posterior mediastinal artery which is from aorta in thorax, inferior phrenic artery a branch from abdominal aorta

The parietal pleura mainly drains into the Azygos vein, and from there, it flows into the Superior vena cava. Some of the venous blood from the diaphragmatic pleura also drains into the inferior vena cava.

The diaphragmatic pleura's lymph drains into the mediastinal, parasternal, para-aortic (phrenic), and celiac nodes and the costal part of the parietal pleura's lymph drains into the parasternal nodes anteriorly and the intercostal nodes posteriorly.

VISCERAL PLEURA:

The Bronchial arteries at the hilum creates a circle around the primary bronchus. Branches from this circular structure provide blood supply to the visceral pleura that covers the mediastinum, interlobar and apical surfaces of the lung, and a portion of the base surface of the diaphragm.

Venous blood from visceral pleura is drains into pulmonary veins

The lymphatic drainage of the visceral pleura is initially via the subpleural lymphatic plexus. Lymph can pass via segmental or intersegmental lymphatic pathways, and sometimes via peri bronchial lymphatic pathways

NERVE SUPPLY:

Intercostal nerves innervate the diaphragmatic parietal pleurae's costal and peripheral regions. The mediastinal and central areas of the diaphragmatic parietal pleurae are innervated by the phrenic nerve (C3 C4). Pain is referred to the lower neck and shoulder tip on the affected side, specifically within the C3 and C4 dermatomes, when the central

diaphragmatic pleura is irritated. Pain is also referred to the similarly innervated part of the thoracic or abdominal wall when the intercostal nerves are irritated.

PHYSIOLOGY²⁵

The pleural space experiences negative pressure in relation to the atmosphere (approximately -0.66kpa at functional residual capacity) during normal inhalation. The space would tend to draw in capillary fluid and gas from the surrounding tissue. The force generated by the respiratory muscles of the lung is transmitted by the pleura. The parietal space regularly transfers low protein fluid to the pleural space. The turnover of proteins and particles is much slower as they are absorbed by lymphatic vessels that open into the parietal pleura. The pressure on the surface of the pleura increased by about 0.5 centimeters of water column in vertical distance from the top to the bottom of the lung. The pleural fluid undergoes a dynamic process, with 30-75% of its water being replaced every hour during regular breathing.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:^{26,27}

The fluid is formed by plasma filtration across the capillary walls and pleural mesothelial cells in the parietal membranes, which follows a hydrostatic pressure gradient. Lymphatics that pass through the parietal membranes actively drain the pleural spaces, creating a negative hydrostatic pressure in the pleural space. The abnormal accumulation of pleural fluid occurs when the balance between the production and absorption of pleural fluid is disrupted for one of the following reasons.

MECHANISM WHICH LEADS TO ACCUMULATION OF PLEURAL FLUID

1. Increase in hydrostatic pressure in the microvascular circulation
2. Decrease in oncotic pressure in the microvascular circulation

3. Decrease in pressure in the pleural space
4. Increase in permeability of the pleural membrane
5. Decrease in lymphatic drainage from the pleural space
6. Movement of fluid from peritoneum
7. Thoracic duct rupture

NORMAL COMPOSITION OF THE PLEURAL FLUID ²⁸:

Cells/mm ³	1000-5000
Volume	0.1-0.2 ml/Kg
Mesothelial cells	3 – 70 %
Lymphocytes	2 – 30%
Macrophages	30 –75%
Granulocytes	10 %
Protein	1 – 2 g/ dL
Albumin	~ plasma level
Glucose	~ plasma level
pH	7.60-7.64
LDH	< 50% of plasma level

DEFINITION ^{2,23}

Pleural effusion is characterized by the pathological accumulation of fluid in the pleural space.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

The incidence of the pleural effusion is expected to be at least 1.5 million cases per year²⁹. The estimated prevalence in industrialised countries is 320 per 100,000 population, with aetiologies varying according to the prevalence of underlying disorders³⁰.

The most common causes are congestive heart failure and parapneumonic effusion³¹. The other common causes include malignant pleural effusion, pulmonary embolism and viral illness²⁹.

CAUSES OF TRANSUDATIVE PLEURAL EFFUSION³²:

1. Congestive heart failure
2. Hepatic hydrothorax
3. Nephrotic syndrome
4. Peritoneal dialysis
5. Myxedema
6. Pericardial disease
7. Central venous obstruction
8. Pulmonary venoocclusive disease
9. Urinothorax
10. Subarachnoid pleural fistula
11. Hypoalbuminemia
12. Iatrogenic

CAUSES OF EXUDATIVE PLEURAL EFFUSION³²:

- Neoplastic diseases
 - i. Metastatic disease
 - ii. Pyothorax – associated lymphoma
 - iii. Mesothelioma
 - iv. Primary effusion lymphoma
- Infectious diseases
 - i. Bacterial infections
 - ii. Tuberculosis
 - iii. Parasitic infections
 - iv. Viral infections
 - v. Fungal infections
 - vi. Actinomycosis & nocardiosis
- Gastrointestinal disease
 - i. Pancreatic disease
 - ii. Esophageal perforation
 - iii. Abscess – subhepatic, intrasplenic, intrahepatic
 - iv. Post-abdominal surgery and post-liver transplant
 - v. Diaphragmatic hernia
 - vi. Endoscopic variceal sclerosis
 - vii. Bilious pleural effusion
- Pulmonary embolization
- Inflammatory diseases
 - i. Rheumatoid pleuritis
 - ii. Lupus pleuritis

- iii. Immunoglobulin G4 related disease
 - iv. Sarcoidosis
 - v. Asbestos related disease
 - vi. Uremia
 - vii. Post cardiac injury syndrome
 - viii. Post coronary artery bypass surgery
 - ix. Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangitis
 - x. Granulomatosis with polyangiitis
 - xi. Sjogren syndrome
 - xii. Acute eosinophilic pneumonia
- Drug-induced pleural disease – Nitrofurantoin, Procarbazine, Dantrolene, Methysergide, Amiodarone, Ergot drugs, Dasatinib , Interleukin-2 , Methotrexate, Clozapine
 - Miscellaneous diseases and conditions
 - i. Lung transplantation
 - ii. Meigs syndrome
 - iii. Endometriosis
 - iv. Ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome
 - v. Trapped lung
 - vi. Yellow nail syndrome
 - vii. Misplaced catheters
 - Hemothorax and Chylothorax

CLINICAL FEATURES OF PLEURAL EFFUSION:

Patient's history is usually non-specific, pleural effusion is mostly an incidental finding on radiological examination. Symptom onset is determined by the amount of effusion and mode of onset.³²

Dyspnea on exertion, rather than at rest is the most prevalent symptom of pleural effusion. A pleural effusion occupies space in the thoracic cavity, thereby reducing lung volume. Small to moderate accumulations of fluid in the pleural space cause the lung to move rather than be compressed and do not impact pulmonary function.³³ In contrast, large pleural effusions take up space in the chest cavity that is normally occupied by lung tissue, leading to a decrease in total lung capacities.³⁴

A dry, nonproductive cough may also be a presenting symptom. The mechanism causing the cough is unknown, but it may be related to pleural inflammation or due to stimulation of cough reflex by fluid compressing the lung.³⁵

Pleuritic chest pain in effusion indicates inflammation of the pleura, since pain fibers are most likely present in the parietal pleura but has now been recognized in visceral pleura and adhesions also.³⁶

Further, history of any occupational exposures (e.g., asbestos), exposures to infectious diseases (e.g., tuberculosis), and underlying conditions (e.g., congestive heart failure, cirrhosis, collagen vascular disease, malignancy), medication history may be important, as they provide clue in the diagnosis of cause of pleural effusion.³⁷

Thoracentesis causes improvement in neuromechanical connection, instantly restoring the length and shape of breathing muscles, particularly the diaphragm leading to immediate improvement in symptoms.³⁷

Figure 1: Restoration of normal shape of diaphragm following therapeutic drainage of pleural fluid.

The PLEASE (Pleural effusion and symptom evaluation) project is the broadest and most comprehensive dataset till date on symptoms, cardiorespiratory state, exercise capacity, radiographic and diaphragmatic characteristics in patients with moderate-to-large pleural effusions requiring drainage of fluid and showed that the majority of participants experience improved symptoms, functional capacity, and spirometry, as well as normalization of diaphragm shape and movement.³⁸

The position of the trachea should always be determined in individuals with pleural effusions since it reflects the relationship between pleural pressures in the two hemithoraces. If the effusion spreads throughout the body and is of a significant size, the physical signs are

1. Restriction of respiratory movements on affected side
2. Stony dullness on percussion
3. Absent or diminished vocal resonance and fremitus
4. Tracheal displacement to the opposite side

5. Pleural fluid auscultation typically shows a lack of breath sounds or a decrease in breath sounds. However, at the upper border of effusion, bronchial breath sounds may become pronounced. The increased transmission of breath sounds through the partially atelectatic lung is the reason behind this phenomenon, which is compressed by the fluid..³⁷

The pleural rub consists of rough, creaking, leathery sounds that are audible during late inhalation and early exhalation. It happens when the roughened pleural surfaces rub against each other during breathing and is often associated with localized pain while breathing, which goes away when holding your breath. Pleural rubs frequently arise when pleural effusions shrink in size, either naturally or as a result of the treatment..³⁹

Massive pleural effusion without mediastinal displacement indicates mediastinum fixation, and the following possibilities to ruled out:⁴⁰

- Carcinoma of main bronchus with atelectasis of the ipsilateral lung
- Malignant mesothelioma
- Fixed mediastinum due to neoplastic lymph nodes.

CAUSES OF ASYMPTOMATIC PLEURAL EFFUSION ²³:

- Benign asbestos pleural effusion
- Nephrotic syndrome
- Rheumatoid effusion
- Hypoalbuminemia
- Peritoneal dialysis
- Yellow nail syndrome
- Trapped lung
- Urinothorax

DIAGNOSIS:

CHEST RADIOGRAPH

Pleural effusions are mostly diagnosed via chest radiography and is the most sensitive method.

Features of pleural effusion on chest xray⁴¹:

- Blunting of cardiophrenic angle
- Blunting of costophrenic angle
- Fluid within oblique or horizontal fissures
- With large volume effusions, mediastinal shift occurs away from the effusion
- The classic finding is a uniform opacity with the costophrenic angle obscured and an upper border that curves in an S-shape, known as the Ellis S-shaped curve. The medial radiological illusion occurs because of the partially aerated lung between the front and back fluid layers, resulting in a medial radiological density. On the other hand, the density is higher on the lateral side due to the presence of only fluid. The actual fluid level is horizontal.

Figure 2: Ellis S-shaped curve

Figure 3: Chest X-ray posteroanterior view, with

massive effusion and contralateral mediastinal shift.

- The posteroanterior film should show an evident amount of 200 mL of fluid, while the lateral film can show costophrenic angle blunting when around 50 mL of fluid has accumulated.⁴²

Subpulmonic effusion refers to the presence of fluid in an infra pulmonary location without spilling into costophrenic sulci or extending up the chest wall. Diagnosing these transudates beneath the lung can be challenging on a PA radiograph and may require a lateral decubitus image or ultrasonography.⁴³

Figure 4: Subpulmonic effusion

Loculated effusion-

The formation of adhesions can involve pleural fluid in any location between the parietal and visceral pleura, extending to the interlobar fissures as well as being created between adjacent pleural surfaces. It is most commonly associated with disorders causing severe pleural inflammation, such as empyema, haemothorax, or tuberculous pleuritis. The space that develops between the lung and the chest wall creates a unique D-shaped appearance on a radiograph. The flat part of the D is positioned against the chest wall, and the gentle curve extends inward towards the lung due to the compressible nature of the lung tissue. Absence of air bronchograms help in differentiating from parenchymal infiltrates.⁴⁴

Figure 5: Obliteration of left costophrenic angle with a large pleural-based dome-shaped opacity projecting into lung, suggesting a **loculated pleural effusion**.

Loculation in the fissures-

Fluid encapsulated in the fissure is typically visible in the lateral view and displays a biconvex lens-like shape. This is particularly common in the patients with congestive heart failure, and because the fluid drains spontaneously when the condition is

addressed and these fluid collections are known as “vanishing tumours or pseudotumors” and most commonly occurs in the right horizontal fissure.⁴⁵

Figure 6- Vanishing tumor

THORACIC ULTRASOUND (TUS)

The British Thoracic Society (BTS) Pleural Disease Guidelines propose using TUS before pleural operations as the standard of therapy.⁴⁶

Indications of ultrasonography:⁴⁷

- Fluid accumulation in the pleura- Pleural effusion , Empyema
- Lung disorders- Pneumonia, Atelectasis, Sequestration, Congenital pulmonary airway malformation, Bronchopulmonary foregut malformation
- Diaphragm disorders- Diaphragmatic paralysis, Diaphragmatic hernia or defect
Diaphragmatic rupture
- Vascular disorders- Vascular thrombosis, Vascular malformation
- Masses- Mediastinal, chest wall, and pulmonary masses
- Interventional indications_Thoracentesis, Biopsy of chest mass, Sclerotherapy of lymphatic malformation, Vascular access

- Other indications-Catheter position in vessels, Pneumothorax, Rib fracture, Rib osteomyelitis, Bronchiolitis

Imaging between the ribs is typically done using a phased-array transducer with a low frequency of 2–5 MHz.⁴⁸

Figure 7: Mild pleural effusion

Figure 8: Massive pleural effusion

Several characteristics to be assessed on ultrasound when there is pleural effusion⁴⁹:

- Size of the effusion/ Quantification
- The echogenicity (brightness) of the effusion
 - Provides an indication of its etiology.
 - Echogenic effusions are usually due to exudates, although concentrated transudates can appear echogenic.
 - Anechoic effusions can be transudative or exudative.
- Presence and extent of fibrous septations – seen in exudative effusions either due to infection or malignancy.
- Thickening or nodularity of parietal and visceral pleurae - pleural malignancy

Based on echogenicity on thoracic ultrasound, effusions are subclassified as^{47,49}

- Anechoic – if echo-free spaces were present between the visceral and parietal pleura.

- Complex non septated - if heterogeneous echogenic material were inside the anechoic pleural effusions.
- Complex septated - if fibrin strands or septa were floating inside anechoic pleural effusions
- Homogeneously echogenic – if homogeneously echogenic spaces were present between the visceral and parietal pleura.

Figure 9: Non-echogenic pleural effusion and part of collapsed lung.²

Figure 10: Highly echogenic effusion and the underlying diaphragm.²

Figure 11: Complex septated pleural effusion.

Sonographic signs of pleural fluid: ⁴⁹

Ultrasound can detect even 5-20ml of pleural fluid

- i) spine sign
- ii) jellyfish sign
- iii) sinusoid sign
- iv) quad sign
- v) plankton sign
- vi) hematocrit sign
- vii) loculated effusion

- **SPINE SIGN-** The spine is typically visible in a normal lung, extending to the diaphragm's edge but not beyond it because the air in the lung above the diaphragm blocks the passage of sound waves. Pleural effusions allow sound waves to pass through the pleural fluid, making it possible to see the spine above the diaphragm.
- **JELLY SIGN-** Undulating movement of compressed lung within pleural effusion. Seen when consolidated lung seen floating in pleural effusion

- **SINUSOID SIGN**- The movement of the parietal and visceral pleura causes the distance between them to change as the patient breathes.
- **QUAD SIGN**- A pleural effusion has an anechoic appearance often delineated by the pleural line, the rib shadows and the lung line
- **PLANKTON SIGN**- Effusion with swirling, hyperechoic debris
- **HEMATOCRIT SIGN**- Echogenic layering of material in a pleural effusion

Figure 12: Spine sign

Figure 13: Jelly sign

Figure 14 : Sinusoid sign

Figure 15 : Quad sign

Figure 16 : Plankton sign

Figure 17 : Hematocrit sign

Quantification: In a study conducted by Balik et al., a formula was found to predict the volume of pleural fluid (in ml), which is a product of 20 and distance of separation between parietal and visceral pleura (in mm).⁵⁰

Figure 18: Quantification of pleural effusion

In Roch et al., 2005 study it was concluded that the PLD basal >5 cm corresponding >500 ml effusion volume PLD basal=distance between basal lung and posterior chest wall end expiratorically⁵¹

In a study conducted by Vignon et al. effusion thickness dorsobasal >45 mm right/> 50 mm left corresponding >800 ml effusion volume⁵²

In Goecke and Schwerk et al., study, The semiquantitative estimation of the effusion volume is calculated by⁵³

$$\text{Vol(ml)} = [\text{H} + \text{D(cm)}] \times 70$$

H- Maximum craniocaudal extent of the fluid

D- Shortest distance between caudal margin of lung & dome of diaphragm

A benign pleural effusion is indicated by a lack of malignant radiological characteristics such as circumferential pleural thickening with nodularity involving the mediastinal surface.

COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY:

Computed tomography (CT) scanning, with its cross-sectional images, can be done in cases where anatomy cannot be assessed completely with chest radiographs or ultrasonography.⁵⁴

CT is useful for diagnosing parenchymal lung lesions, masses, and enlarged mediastinal lymph nodes. It can also aid in determining the site of empyema drainage, distinguishing between empyema and lung abscess, and locating the chest tube in unsuccessful empyema drainage.⁴⁹

However, the imaging characteristics of malignancies and infections are similar.

Characteristics on CT scan that are more common in pleural infection (parapneumonic, empyema, and tuberculosis) than malignancy include^{36,37} -

- i. Lentiform configuration of pleural fluid
- ii. Increased density of the extra pleural fat
- iii. Presence of pulmonary consolidation.
- iv. Visceral pleural thickening ('split pleura sign')
- v. Hypertrophy of extrapleural fat (>2 mm)

A CT angiography should be conducted if pulmonary embolism is highly suspected.

The presence of the split pleura sign in a contrast-enhanced CT scan of the chest suggests the presence of pleural thickening. The thickened inner visceral and outer parietal pleura are enhanced, with separation caused by pleural fluid collection.⁵⁵

Figure 19: Contrast-enhanced computed tomography: split pleural sign

MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING (MRI):

Magnetic resonance imaging can detect pleural effusions. Pleural fluid collection is characterised by a low signal intensity on T1-weighted imaging that gradually brightens on T2-weighted imaging. Pleural fluid collections present in various forms, including transudative fluid, chylothorax, hemothorax, or pus, may exhibit slight variations on MRI, but they are not definitive for diagnosis.³⁶

CT and MRI scans for mesothelioma typically yield similar results but MRI is more effective than CT for detecting involvement of chest wall, endothoracic fascia, and diaphragmatic muscle.⁵⁶

POSITRON EMISSION TOMOGRAPHY (PET-CT):

The uptake of 18-fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) has been demonstrated to be elevated in malignant pleural effusions, but PET-CT imaging's ability to differentiate between benign and malignant conditions is hindered by false positives in patients with pleural inflammation, such as pleural infection, or after undergoing talc pleurodesis.⁵⁷

PET-CT imaging does not have a role in routine investigation of pleural effusions, although, like dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI, there is increasing data suggesting a possible role in monitoring the response to the treatment for pleural mesothelioma.⁵⁷

THORACOSCOPY:

When dealing with symptomatic exudative pleural effusion and an inconclusive or negative diagnostic pleural aspiration, it is advisable to opt for thoracoscopy. It also has an added advantage of performing pleurodesis at the time of procedure if required.⁵⁸

THORACENTESIS (PLEURAL ASPIRATION)

Thoracentesis should be performed in all patients having pleural effusion of unknown etiology, with effusion more than 1 cm in height on lateral decubitus radiography, ultrasonography, or CT.

It is an important diagnostic and therapeutic procedure in the examination and management of pleural effusion. Immediately preceding pleural intervention for suspected fluid, the use of TUS has been strongly supported as a way to enhance patient safety, decrease the occurrence of iatrogenic effects, and improve diagnosis.⁶⁰

PLEURAL FLUID ANALYSIS:

Pleural fluid biochemical studies are potential diagnostic methods for pleural effusion because they are inexpensive, have a quick turnaround time, and are objective.

DIFFERENTIATING BETWEEN AN EXUDATIVE AND TRANSUDATIVE

PLEURAL FLUID:

For years, a pleural fluid protein level of 3.0 g/dL was employed to distinguish between transudative and exudative pleural effusions. Exudative pleural effusions were identified by means of protein level above 3.0 g/dL.³⁶

To distinguish between transudative and exudative pleural effusions, the pleural fluid protein should be assessed. This is typically sufficient if the serum protein in patient is normal and pleural protein is less than 25 g/L or more than 35 g/L. If not, the light's criteria should be applied.

LIGHT'S CRITERIA^{36,37}

The pleural fluid is an exudate, if one or more of following criteria are met:

1. Pleural fluid LDH / Serum LDH > 0.6
2. Pleural fluid protein / Serum Protein > 0.5
3. Pleural fluid LDH more than 2/3rd the upper limits of normal serum LDH

Several biomarkers, including cholesterol, NT-proBNP, CRP, bilirubin, cholinesterase, albumin, and protein gradients, have been proposed as alternative diagnostic tools to LDH and protein in pleural fluid and serum.

Valdes et al. found that the ratio of pleural fluid cholesterol to serum cholesterol is more than 0.3 (sensitivity 92.5%, specificity 87.6%) and it was discovered that using 0.4 as the cutoff threshold resulted in 100% specificity and 86.04% sensitivity.⁶¹

Characteristics of Exudative effusion³⁵

- Pleural fluid to serum bilirubin ratio >0.6

- Difference in the pleural fluid and serum albumin level <1.2 g/dL
- Pleural fluid cholesterol >60 mg/dL
- High pleural fluid viscosity
- Elevated levels of oxidative stress markers, soluble leukocyte selectin, cytokines
- Pleural fluid-to-serum cholinesterase ratio >0.23

Characteristics of transudative pleural effusion

- Clear, straw coloured, non viscid, odourless
- Total count $<1,000/\text{mm}^3$
- Pleural fluid glucose similar to serum glucose level
- Low pleural fluid amylase
- High pleural fluid pH

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PLEURAL FLUID:

After performing thoracentesis procedure, the colour, viscosity, odour and turbidity of the pleural fluid should be noted. The appearance can be classified as serous, blood-tinged, frank blood, or purulent.

If the pleural fluid is cloudy or milky, it should be centrifuged. If the supernatant is clear, the turbid fluid was caused by cell debris, and indicates higher probability of empyema. If turbidity persists, it is due to excessive lipid content, and likely due to chylothorax or pseudo-chylothorax.⁶²

A pleural fluid hematocrit of at least 50% of the peripheral blood measurement indicates a hemothorax.⁶³

Appearance of pleural fluid ⁶⁴

Pleural fluid finding	Potential Etiology
Pale yellow	Most transudates
Turbid	Inflammatory exudates
Pus	Empyema
Bloody	Haemothorax
Bile stained	Biliary fistula
Milky	Chylothorax/Pseudo-chylothorax
Anchovy sauce like fluid	Ruptured amoebic abscess
Yellow to green	Rheumatoid pleurisy
Black	Aspergillus niger infection
Urine	Urinothorax

Pleural fluid glucose⁶⁵-

The molecular weight of glucose is small, allowing it to move from the bloodstream to the pleural fluid through simple diffusion across the endothelium-mesothelium membranes. Hence, glucose concentration in pleural fluid is comparable to the concentration of glucose in blood.

A low concentration of glucose is described as ratio of pleural fluid glucose to blood glucose of less than 0.5, which is found in exudative pleural effusions caused by malignant pleural effusion, parapneumonic effusion, tuberculous pleuritis, rheumatoid pleural effusion.

Pleural fluid pH-

If the pleural fluid pH ≤ 7.2 , it is suggestive of exudative effusion and seen in - complicated parapneumonic effusion, systemic acidosis, esophageal rupture, malignant pleural disease, rheumatoid pleuritis, tuberculous pleuritis, hemothorax, paragonimiasis, lupus pleuritis, or urinothorax.³⁶

In cases of transudative pleural effusions, the pH of the pleural fluid is typically higher than the pH of the blood at the same time, possibly due to the active transportation of bicarbonate from the blood into the pleural space.⁶⁶

The pleural fluid pH can predict the prognosis of patients with parapneumonic effusions

- If the pH ≤ 7.2 , the patient has complicated parapneumonic effusion or pleural infection and should undergo tube thoracostomy.
- If the pH is between 7.2 & 7.4, indicates an intermediate risk of complex parapneumonic effusion or pleural infection. Pleural fluid LDH to be measured and pleural enhancement on CT scan or septations on ultrasound scan to be seen.
- If pH is ≥ 7.4 , indicates low risk and no indication of immediate drainage.^{60,67}

Differential cell count

Pleural fluid cell count and differential count may help narrow the differential diagnosis. However, there is no evidence that pleural fluid cell count and differentials significantly modify management, and overlapping profiles of diverse effusion forms decrease their discriminatory strength.⁶⁸

Polymorphonuclear cells predominate in case of an acute process affecting the pleura surfaces.^{23,68}. Causes include -

Parapneumonic effusions

Pulmonary embolism

Systemic lupus erythematosus vasculitis

Acute tuberculosis,

Empyema

If the pleural fluid differential count reveals a predominant lymphocytosis (>50%), the likely diagnosis are tuberculosis and malignancy.²³ Causes are-

Malignancy causes-

Carcinoma

Mesothelioma

Lymphoma

Benign causes- Tuberculosis

Chylothorax

Yellow nail syndrome

Trapped lung

Hypothyroidism

Sarcoidosis

Autoimmune disorders

A pleural effusion is considered eosinophilic when the pleural fluid contains 10% or higher eosinophils.^{32,68} Pleural fluid eosinophilia can be present in a variety of conditions, including

Drug-induced pleurisy,

Benign asbestos pleural effusion,

Churg- strauss syndrome,

Parasite infestation,

Coccidiomycosis

Pneumothorax

Adenosine deaminase (ADA)-

ADA catalyses the conversion of adenosine to inosine. In general, a cutoff level of 40-45 U/L is employed, with higher values indicating tuberculosis.³⁵ The sensitivity of ADA levels above 70 IU/L in tuberculous pleural effusion is 98%, and the specificity is 96%.⁶⁹

Immunosuppressed patients and renal transplant patients with tuberculous pleuritis also have high levels of pleural fluid ADA.^{70,71}

In addition to TB, rheumatoid pleuritis and empyema are the leading causes of increased ADA.^{72,73} Inclusion of pleural fluid lymphocyte-to-neutrophil ratio (of more than 0.75) to the diagnostic criteria for tuberculous pleuritis improves the specificity of the test.⁷⁴

Two isoenzymes are present in ADA: ADA1, which is produced by lymphocytes, neutrophils, monocytes, and macrophages, and ADA2, which is exclusively present in monocytes and macrophages. ADA activity rises in tuberculous pleuritis mainly due to ADA2, as lymphocytes make up the majority of cells in the pleural fluid. The results suggest that the pleural fluid ADA comes from pleural tissues rather than from cells within the fluid.⁷⁵

NT Pro BNP:

Pleural fluid N-terminal prohormone brain natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP) is useful when considering heart failure as a cause in unilateral pleural effusions when the levels more than 1500pg/ml but not superior to NT-proBNP in serum and therefore should not be ordered routinely.³²

Figure 20: Algorithm for distinguishing transudative from exudative pleural effusions

Figure 20: Algorithm for evaluating exudates with an unknown etiology

MANAGEMENT:

THORACOCENTESIS:

Thoracentesis plays a significant role in both diagnosing and treating pleural effusions and showed that it improves the symptoms, functional capacity and spirometry and also normalises the shape of diaphragm and movement in the majority of the patients.^{38,76}

Patients suspected of having a malignant pleural effusion (MPE) should provide 25–50 mL of pleural fluid for cytological analysis.⁶⁰

INDICATIONS OF CHEST TUBE ⁷⁷:

- I. Pus in pleural space
- II. Gramstain of pleural fluid positive
- III. Pleural fluid pH <7.0
- IV. Pleural fluid glucose below 40mg/dl
- V. Pleural fluid loculated
- VI. Pleural fluid culture positive
- VII. Pleural fluid LDH >3x upperlimit for serum
- VIII. Massive pleural effusion

ANTIBIOTICS:

Six months course of antitubercular therapy indicated in tubercular pleural effusion.

Treatment of patients with PPE and empyema relies upon the selection of appropriate antibiotics. Patients with community acquired pneumonia typically require coverage for Streptococcus species and anaerobes (e.g., Bacteroides), while patients with a hospital-acquired infection will, at least initially, require therapy directed at more resistant pathogens (e.g., methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus and Enterobacter)³⁷

INTRAPLEURAL THERAPY: ⁶⁰

Pleural infections lead to fibrin depositions and septations. Intrapleural therapies can be given to reduce the septations which improves the drainage thereby attempting to avoid the need for the surgical procedures which are invasive. Intrapleural therapies can be done with fibrinolytics, combined intrapleural enzyme therapy, intrapleural antibiotics and saline irrigation.

Consider using a combination of tissue plasminogen activator (TPA) and DNase to treat pleural infection when the initial chest tube drainage has stopped and a residual pleural collection remains.

- When intrapleural TPA and DNase therapy or surgery is not appropriate, saline irrigation can be an option for treating pleural infection.
- When TPA plus DNase is being administered, the prescribed dosage should be 10 mg of TPA twice daily and 5 mg of DNase twice daily for a duration of 3 days, as per the data from a randomized controlled trial.

SURGICAL APPROACH: Considering VATS access is preferable to thoracotomy for adults when surgically treating pleural infection.

Indications:

- I. Diagnosis of pleural effusion
- II. Drainage of empyema
- III. Pleurodesis
- IV. Diagnosis of a suspicious pulmonary nodule
- V. Biopsy of the pleura Lung biopsy for diagnosis of interstitial lung disease
- VI. Resection of pulmonary metastatic nodules

- VII. Resection of primary lung carcinoma
- VIII. Biopsy of mediastinal lymph nodes
- IX. Resection of blebs or bullae for treatment of spontaneous pneumothorax
- X. Drainage of pericardial effusion

PROCALCITONIN:

Procalcitonin, the precursor of the hormone calcitonin, is utilized as a biomarker to assist in identifying bacterial infection or sepsis.⁷⁷

It was first described by Le Moullec et al. in 1984, although its diagnostic relevance was not recognised until 1993.⁷⁸ A positive correlation was then demonstrated between high serum levels of PCT and patients who tested positive for bacterial infection and sepsis in 1993 by Assicot et al.⁷⁹

The United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) has approved the use of PCT assays to initiate or discontinue antibiotics in patients with lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs), as well as to discontinue antibiotics in patients with sepsis.⁸⁰

Structure-

Procalcitonin is a 14.5 kDa peptide consisting of 116 amino acids, consisting of three components - the amino terminus with 57 amino acids, 33 amino acids in immature calcitonin and calcitonin carboxyl-terminus peptide1(CCP-1) also called katacalcin containing 21 amino acids .⁸¹

Figure 21: Synthesis of procalcitonin

Synthesis

Calcitonin 1 gene (CALC-1) on short arm of chromosome 11 is responsible for the synthesis of procalcitonin. The CALC-1 gene is generally transcribed and translated only in thyroid C-cells and, to a lesser extent, other neuroendocrine cells.⁸¹

The original product formed is 141 amino acid chain of Pre- PCT, which binds to endoplasmic reticulum and is cleaved by endopeptidase to produce PCT, which is subsequently processed to form the mature calcitonin molecule.⁸²

When there's a bacterial infection, cytokines like interleukin-6 (IL6), tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) trigger the production of procalcitonin in all parenchymal tissues.⁸³

There is accumulation of PCT in these tissues as they lack the ability to cleave PCT to its mature form, calcitonin.⁸⁴ Interferon- γ , secreted in response to viral infection, reduces PCT synthesis. This attribute makes PCT a more specific marker for bacterial infections.⁸⁵

Healthy individuals normally have a serum PCT concentration of less than 0.1 microgram/L.⁸⁶

Following an infection, PCT can be detected in 3-4 hours, following release of TNF- α and IL-6 at 90 minutes and 3 hours, respectively. It has a half-life of around 24 hours and reaches peak concentration between 6 and 12 hours.⁸⁷

Physiological importance of procalcitonin:

Based on animal models or on in vitro experiments, following roles of PCT has been hypothesised⁸²

- Calcium metabolism
- Cytokine network and modulation of nitric oxide (NO) synthesis
- Analgesic effects

Pleural fluid PCT shows a positive correlation with blood PCT, indicating that pleural fluid PCT originates from blood PCT.⁸⁸

Factors which cause raised procalcitonin levels:⁸⁷

- Recent major surgery
- Severe trauma
- Severe burns
- Prolonged cardiogenic shock
- Fungal and malarial infections
- Medications which stimulate cytokine release such as IL-2, okt3, alemtuzumab, antilymphocyte globulins, and granulocyte transfusion

- Paraneoplastic syndromes due to medullary thyroid carcinomas and small cell lung carcinomas
- During peritoneal dialysis
- Cirrhosis particularly Child-Pugh Class C
- Chronic kidney disease

Newborns exhibit higher baseline PCT levels compared to adults. PCT levels rise even more in the initial 24 hours after birth and continue to stay elevated during the first two days of life.⁸⁹

Figure 22: Age specific 95% reference range for PCT in healthy neonates.

Figure 23: Patients with early onset infection within 48 hours of age had PCT values obtained.⁹⁰

A low or normal PCT may not always denote absence of bacterial infection. This may be the case especially in the early phase of bacterial infection, in localised infections like empyema, osteomyelitis or in subacute infective endocarditis.⁸⁸

Assay-

All of the currently available PCT quantification assays use immunoassay techniques. The BRAHMS PCT LIA®, a manual luminometric immunoassay from Thermo Fisher in Hennigsdorf, Germany, was the first commercially available procalcitonin assay.⁹¹

The BRAHMS PCT Kryptor® (Thermo Fisher, Hennigsdorf, Germany) which is more sensitive and rapid automated assay was the first one to be certified by the FDA in 2008 for use in the diagnosis of severe sepsis and septic shock.⁹¹

The chemiluminescent microparticle immunoassay (CMIA) technique is utilised to quantify PCT levels in human serum and plasma.⁹²

PCT can be tested at the point of care using an immunochromatographic method. A coloured band become visible on the test strip 30 minutes after 200 microliters of serum or plasma are applied and the intensity of the band is compared to a reference card and the values are reported as less than 0.5, 0.5 to 2.0, 2.0 to 10, and >10 µg/L.⁹³

OTHER STUDIES:

Peter T Evan et al. in **2021** conducted a study to detect the use of Thoracic Ultrasound to Predict transudative and exudative pleural effusion and concluded that complex homogeneous or septated appearances were highly distinctive and indicative of exudative fluids and reliable distinction between transudative and exudative fluid could not be done using anechoic pictures.⁹⁴

In **2016**, **Rahul Khosla Md et al.** studied that investigating the function of pleural procalcitonin in determining hospitalized patients' risk stratification, antibiotic stewardship, and severity of illness is critical since PCT is a novel biomarker for identifying infected pleural effusions and also concluded that subgroup analysis also

showed a higher procalcitonin levels in exudative effusions of the infectious diseases group as compared to exudative effusions of malignant or paramalignant etiology in the noninfectious group.¹⁵

In a study conducted by **Fiona J McCann et al.2012**, that procalcitonin is a biomarker specific for infection and is not affected by non-infective inflammation. Even after accounting for systemic inflammation, procalcitonin is a better indicator of pleural disorders than CRP in distinguishing infectious from non-infective conditions.⁹⁵

In the year **2018, Naoki Watanabe et al.** study concluded that procalcitonin, presepsin and CRP in pleural fluid may be useful as additional tools in the evaluation of pleural effusions to support with the differential diagnosis and also support the possible use of pleural fluid procalcitonin as a diagnostic tool by indicating that it appears to be higher in cases of parapneumonic effusion than in other pleural effusions.⁹⁶

A study on the conducted on the value of ultrasound in detecting the nature of pleural effusion in **2022 by Ting Wang, MD et al.** concluded that empyema is the most prevalent disease-causing exudates and has the highest proportion of positive results on ultrasonographic imaging. Sonographic signs of pleural effusion, such as echogenicity, septation, and pleural thickness, may be more suggestive of exudates.⁹⁷

In **2017, Entsar R Ahmed et al.** studied the role of ultrasonography in diagnosing pleural effusion in 84 cases. Transthoracic ultrasonography is a quick, easy,

affordable, radiation-free technique for evaluating pleural diseases. The study also stated that TUS was superior to CT in the detection of septations and superior to chest radiography in identifying consolidation, pleural mass, encysted pleural effusion, and pleural thickening.⁹⁸

Nilam J. Soni, MD et al. conducted a study in **2015** on ultrasound in the diagnosis and management of pleural effusions. The study has proved that ultrasound has the benefits of avoiding ionizing radiation, low costs and bedside availability and also improves patient safety by lowering complications and raising the success rate of pleural draining procedures. Point-of-care pleural ultrasonography thorax is expected to become the standard diagnostic technique for evaluating and managing patients with pleural effusions as clinical efficacy trials show its true value.⁴⁹

In another study by **Leila A. Helala et al. 2015**, it was concluded that in the respiratory intensive care unit, ultrasonography is a useful and effective way to assess pleural diseases, especially pleural effusion. Pleural procedures guided by ultrasound have proven to be effective, with favorable outcomes and minimal side effects.⁹⁹

In **2020** a study conducted by **Verdah Ahmed et al.** fibrin strands, concluded that ultrasonography of the chest helps in the prediction of the etiology and also presence of septations, and loculations, plankton sign, are sonographic signs are very specific for diagnosing exudative pleural effusions.¹⁰⁰

In a study conducted by **Bulent Akkurt et al. in 2019**, it was found that the procalcitonin values in the parapneumonic effusions for serum and pleural fluid had

no diagnostic value. There was not a significant difference in the ratio of pleural fluid to serum procalcitonin between the two groups and there was no association found between procalcitonin levels and thoracic ultrasound pictures.¹⁰¹

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SOURCE OF DATA:

- All pleural effusion patients undergoing evaluation in the department of Respiratory Medicine OPD/ wards in BLDE[DU] Shri B M Patil medical college, Hospital and Research center, Vijayapura will be included in the study.

STUDY DESIGN:

- Hospital-based cross-sectional study.

STUDY PERIOD:

18 Months

STATISTICAL DATA:

SAMPLE SIZE

Using G*Power ver. 3.1.9.4 software for sample size calculation, The CXR Sensitivity of Pleural effusion is 72%, this study requires a sample size of 89. So to achieve a power of 99% for detecting a difference in Proportion (Exact - Proportion: Difference from constant (binomial test, one sample case)) with a 5% level of significance.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data obtained is entered in a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analyses are performed using a statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) (Version 20).

Results are presented as Mean, SD, counts and percentages, and diagrams.

For normally distributed continuous variables between the two groups will be compared using an independent sample t-test.

For not normally distributed variables, the Mann-Whitney U test is used.

For Categorical variables between the two groups are compared using the Chi-square test/Fisher's exact

test $P < 0.05$ will be considered statistically significant. All statisticals are performed in two-tailed.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. All people aged above 18 years.
2. All OPD and IPD cases having Pleural effusion

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Patients with contraindication to pleural aspiration procedure
2. People aged below 18 years
3. Pregnant and lactating women.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA:

All pleural effusion patients will be subjected to Ultrasound thorax and Diagnostic Pleural Fluid analysis. Depending on the ultrasound findings below, corresponding conventional or surgical management of pleural effusion will be considered.

**ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION AND FOLLOWING MANAGEMENT OF
PLEURAL EFFUSION**

ULTRASOUND THORAX	CONSERVATIVE MANAGEMENT THERAPEUTIC PLEURAL ASPIRATION	SURGICAL MANAGEMENT ICD TUBE INSERTION UNDERWATER SEAL	SURGICAL MANAGEMENT THORACOTOMY/ VATS DECORTICATIONS
Massive effusion with no septations and loculation		Yes	
Moderate effusion with no septations and loculations	Yes		
Minimal Effusion	Yes		
Effusion with internal echoes		Yes	
Effusion with thin internal septations		Yes +/- intrapleural fibrinolytic agent	
Effusion with thick internal septations			Yes
Effusion with a single locule		Yes	
Effusion with multiple locules			Yes

ULTRASOUND PATTERN AND NATURE OF EFFUSION

PATTERN	TRANSUDATIVE	EXUDATIVE
ANECHOGENIC	Yes	Yes
ECHOGENIC		Yes
COMPLEX NON SEPTATED	Yes	Yes
COMPLEX SEPTATED		Yes
THICKENED PLEURA AND ASSOCIATED PARENCHYMAL LESIONS		Yes

PLEURAL FLUID ANALYSIS

Diagnostic pleural tapping to be done and fluid to be sent for

Pleural fluid gram stain, Zn stain, aerobic culture, antibiotic sensitivity, Cbnaat for TB.

Pleural fluid - cell type, cell count, and malignant cells

Pleural fluid- protein, sugar, chloride, ADA, LDH

PLEURAL FLUID PROCALCITONIN LEVELS: Detection by human procalcitonin ELISA

kit and analysed in the Tecan company ELISA reader.

INVESTIGATIONS

1. Chest Xray PA View
2. USG thorax
3. Pleural fluid analysis
 - Microbiology-gram stain, Zn stain, aerobic culture and antibiotic sensitivity, cbnaat for Tb.
 - Pathology/ Cytology– cell type, cell count and malignant cells
 - Biochemistry- Protein, Sugar, Chloride, ADA, LDH
4. Pleural fluid Procalcitonin levels

RESULTS

GRAPH 1: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS

Of 89 cases, 32 patients (35.9%) with pleural effusion had anechoic finding, while 19 patients (21.3%) had complex non-septate finding, and 35 patients (39.3%) had complex septate finding and 3 (3.3%) patients had homogenous echoes finding. The distribution of cases is shown in graph 1.

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS WITH RESPECT TO LIGHTS CRITERIA

In 59 patients with exudates, Thoracic ultrasonography showed anechoic appearance in 9 patients (15.3%), complex non septate appearance in 13 patients (22%), complex septate finding in 34 patients (57.6%) and complex homogenous sign in 3 patients (5.1%). In 30

patients with transudates, 23 patients had anechoic appearance, 6 patients had complex non septate and 1 patient had complex homogenous sign accounting to 76.7%, 20% and 3.3% respectively. (Table 1)

USG FINDINGS		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total
		Exudative PE	Transudative PE	
Anechoic	Count	9	23	32
	% within GROUPS	15.3%	76.7%	36.0%
Complex non septate	Count	13	6	19
	% within GROUPS	22.0%	20.0%	21.3%
Complex septate	Count	34	1	35
	% within GROUPS	57.6%	3.3%	39.3%
Homogenous echoes	Count	3	0	3
	% within GROUPS	5.1%	0.0%	3.4%
Total	Count	59	30	89
	% within GROUPS	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

GRAPH 2: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO SEPTATIONS ON ULTRASOUND THORAX

Of 89 cases, 7 (7.9%) cases had thick septations and 28 (31.5%) cases had thin septations and 54(60.6%) were with nil septations. The distribution of cases is shown in graph 2.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO SEPTATIONS ON ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS WITH RESPECT TO LIGHTS CRITERIA

Of 59 cases of exudative cases, 7 cases had thick septations and 27 cases had thin septations and 25 cases were with nil septations. Of 30 transudative cases, 1 case had thin septation and 29 cases had nil septations. The distribution of cases is shown in table 2.

SEPTATIONS	Exudative PE	Transudative PE	Total
Nil	25	29	54
	46.3%	53.7%	100%
Thick	7	0	7
	100%	0	100%
Thin	27	1	28
	96.43%	3.57%	100%
Total	59	30	89
	66.29%	33.71%	100%

GRAPH 3: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO QUANTITY ON ULTRASOUND THORAX:

Of 89 patients with pleural effusion, 21(23.6%) cases were found to have gross effusion, 14 (15.7%) cases had mild effusion and 24 (60.7%)cases had moderate effusion. The distribution was given in Graph 3

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO QUANTITY ON ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS WITH RESPECT TO LIGHTS CRITERIA

In 59 patients with exudates, Thoracic ultrasonography showed gross effusion in patients 6(10.2%), moderate effusion in 43 patients (72.9%), mild effusion in 10 patients (16.9%). In 30 patients with transudates, 15 patients had gross effusion, 11 patients had moderate effusion and 4 patients had mild effusion accounting to 50%, 13.3% and 36.7% respectively. (Table 3)

QUANTITY	LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total
	Exudative PE	Transudative PE	

	Gross	Count	6	15	21
		% within GROUPS	10.2%	50.0%	23.6%
	Mild	Count	10	4	14
		% within GROUPS	16.9%	13.3%	15.7%
	Moderate	Count	43	11	54
		% within GROUPS	72.9%	36.7%	60.7%
Total	Count	59	30	89	
	% within GROUPS	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

GRAPH 4: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO SITE OF EFFUSION ON ULTRASOUND THORAX:

In 89 cases, 15 cases (16.9%) had bilateral effusion, 25 cases (28.1%) had left sided effusion and 49 cases (55%) had right sided effusion

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO SITE OF EFFUSION ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH RESPECT TO LIGHTS CRITERIA

In 59 patients with exudates, Ultrasound showed bilateral effusion in patients 7(11.9%), left sided effusion in 19 patients (32.2%), right sided effusion in 33 patients (55.9%). In 30 patients with transudates, 8 patients had bilateral effusion, 6 patients had left sided effusion and 16 patients had right sided effusion accounting to 26.7%, 20% and 53.3% respectively.

(Table 4)

SITE		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total
		Exudative PE	Transudative PE	
Bilateral	Count	7	8	15
	% within GROUPS	11.9%	26.7%	16.9%
Left	Count	19	6	25
	% within GROUPS	32.2%	20.0%	28.1%
Right	Count	33	16	49
	% within GROUPS	55.9%	53.3%	55%
Total	Count	59	30	89
	% within GROUPS	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

GRAPH 5: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO THICKENED PLEURA ON ULTRASOUND THORAX:

In 89 cases, 16 cases had thickened pleura, 73 cases were not presented with thickened pleura accounting to 17.98% and 82.02% respectively. The distribution is given in the graph 4

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO THICKENED PLEURA ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH RESPECT TO LIGHTS CRITERIA

16 out of 59 cases with exudative effusion were found to have thickened pleura while transudative effusion cases did not have any thickened pleura finding.(Table 5)

THICKENED PLEURA		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total
		Exudative PE	Transudative PE	
PRESENT	Count	16	0	16
	% within GROUPS	27%	0	17.98%
ABSENT	Count	43	30	73

	% within GROUPS	73%	100%	82.02%
Total	Count	59	30	89
	% within GROUPS	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

GRAPH 6: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES BASED ON ETIOLOGIES OF PLEURAL EFFUSION CASES

Among the 89 cases, TB is the most frequent etiology at 28.09%, followed by Parapneumonic Effusion at 13.48%, Empyema, HF, and CLD each at 12.36%, with lower frequencies for Malignancy 10.11%, CKD 10.11%, and Pulmonary Embolism 1.12%. The distribution is given in the below graph

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO ETIOLOGIES OF PLEURAL EFFUSION WITH RESPECT TO LIGHTS CRITERIA

In patients with exudates, the diseases were TB [25 cases], Malignancy [9 cases], Empyema [11 cases], Parapneumonic effusions [12 cases], pulmonary embolism [1 case] and CLD [1 cases]. The diseases in transudates were CLD [10 cases] , CKD [9 cases], Heart failure [11 cases] as shown in the below table.

ETIOLOGY	TRANSUDATES	EXUDATES
TB	0	25
MALIGNANCY	0	9
EMPHYEMA	0	11
HF	11	0
CKD	9	0
CLD	10	1
PARAPNEUMONIC EFFUSION	0	12
PULM.EMBOLISM	0	1

GRAPH 7: DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF MALIGNANT EFFUSION CASES

In the subpopulation of malignant pleural effusion cases, the proportion of Anechogenic appearance, complex non septate appearance , complex septate appearance, homogenous echoes and pleural thickening were 5/9, 1/9, 3/9, 0, 0 respectively.

GRAPH 8: DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF TUBERCULAR EFFUSION CASES

In the subpopulation of tubercular pleural effusion cases, the proportion of anechoic appearance, complex non septate appearance, complex septate appearance, homogenous echoes and pleural thickening were 2/15, 8/15, 13/25, 2/25, 2/25 respectively.

GRAPH 9 : DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF EMPYEMA CASES

In the subpopulation of empyema cases, the proportion of complex septate appearance and pleural thickening on ultrasound thorax were 11/11 and 11/11 respectively.

GRAPH 10 : DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF PULMONARY EMBOLISM EFFUSION CASES

The one pulmonary embolism effusion case in the study had complex non-septate appearance.

GRAPH 11: DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF PARAPNEUMONIC EFFUSION CASES

In the subpopulation of parapneumonic effusion cases, the proportion of anechoic appearance, complex non septate appearance, complex septate appearance, homogenous echoes and pleural thickening were 1/12, 3/12, 7/12, 1/12, 3/12 respectively.

GRAPH 12: DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF HEARTFAILURE EFFUSION CASES

In the subpopulation of CLD effusion cases, the proportion of anechoic appearance, complex non septate appearance were 9/11 and 2/11 respectively.

GRAPH 13: DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF CLD EFFUSION CASES

In the subpopulation of CLD effusion cases, the proportion of anechoic appearance, complex non septate appearance, complex septate appearance were 8/11, 2/11, 1/11 respectively.

GRAPH 14: DISTRIBUTION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS OF CKD EFFUSION CASES

In the subpopulation of CKD effusion cases, the proportion of anechoic appearance and complex non septate appearance on ultrasonography were 7/9 and 2/9 respectively.

TABLE 7: CORRELATION OF ANECHOIC FINDING ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA:

- Total anechoic findings in the study were 32
- Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 9 and 23 respectively.
- Causes of exudative pleural effusion-
 - Malignancy - 5
 - Parapneumonic - 1
 - TB- 2
 - CLD- 1
- Causes of transudative pleural effusion-
 - CKD -7
 - CLD-7
 - HF- 9

USG FINDINGS		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			
Anechoic	Count	9	23	32	32.572	0.001
	% within GROUPS	15.3%	76.7%	36.0%		

The p-value of 0.001 indicates a **statistically significant association** between the type of pleural effusion (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of anechogenic findings on ultrasound.

TABLE 8: CORRELATION OF COMPLEX SEPTATE FINDING ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA:

Total complex septate findings in the study were 35

Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 34 and 1 respectively.

Causes of exudative pleural effusion-

- Malignancy - 3
- Parapneumonic - 7
- TB- 13
- Empyema-11

Causes of transudative pleural effusion-

- CLD- 1

USG FINDINGS		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			

Complex septate	Count	34	1	35	24.570	0.001
	% within GROUPS	57.6%	3.3%	39.3%		

The p-value of 0.001 indicates a **statistically significant association** between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of complex septate findings on ultrasound.

TABLE 9: CORRELATION OF COMPLEX NON- SEPTATE FINDING ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA:

- Total complex non septate findings in the study were 19
- Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 13 and 6 respectively.
- Causes of exudative pleural effusion-
 - Malignancy - 1
 - Parapneumonic - 3
 - TB- 8
 - PE- 1
- Causes of transudative pleural effusion
 - CKD -2
 - CLD-2
 - HF- 2

USG FINDINGS	LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
	Exudative	Transudative			

Complex non septate	Count	13	6	19	0.049	0.8248
	% within GROUPS	22.0%	20.0%	21.3%		

The p-value of 0.8248 indicates no statistically significant association between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of complex non-septate findings on ultrasound.

TABLE 10: CORRELATION OF HOMOGENOUS ECHOES FINDING ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA:

Total Homogenous echoes findings in the study were 3

Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 3 and 0 respectively.

Causes of exudative pleural effusion-

- TB – 2
- Parapneumonic - 1

USG FINDINGS		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			
Homogenous echoes	Count	3	0	3	1.579	0.2090
	% within GROUPS	5.1%	0.0%	3.4%		

The p-value of 0.2090 indicates no statistically significant association between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of homogenous echoes on ultrasound.

TABLE 11: CORRELATION OF GROSS PLEURAL EFFUSIONS ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA:

Total Gross findings in the study were 21

Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 6 and 15 respectively.

Causes of exudative pleural effusion-

- Malignancy - 1
- TB- 2
- Empyema-1
- Parapneumonic – 1
- CLD-1

Causes of transudative pleural effusion-

- CLD- 6
- CKD- 6
- HF-3

USG FINDINGS QUANTITY		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			
Gross	Count	6	15	21	10.931	0.009
	% within GROUPS	10.2%	50.0%	23.6%		

The p-value of 0.009 indicates a statistically significant association between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of gross findings on ultrasound.

TABLE 12: CORRELATION OF MODERATE PLEURAL EFFUSIONS ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA

Total Moderate findings in the study were 54

Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 43 and 11 respectively.

Causes of exudative pleural effusion-

- Malignancy - 6
- TB- 15
- Empyema- 10
- Parapneumonic- 11
- PE- 1

Causes of transudative pleural effusion-

- CLD- 4
- CKD- 1
- HF- 6

USG FINDINGS QUANTITY		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			
Moderate	Count	43	11	54	17.501	0.001
	% within GROUPS	72.9%	36.7%	60.7%		

The p-value of 0.001 indicates statistically significant association between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of moderate findings on ultrasound.

TABLE 13: CORRELATION OF MILD PLEURAL EFFUSIONS ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA

Total Mild findings in the study were 14

Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 10 and 4 respectively.

Causes of exudative pleural effusion-

- Malignancy - 2
- TB- 8

Causes of transudative pleural effusion-

- CKD- 2

- HF- 2

USG FINDINGS QUANTITY		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			
Mild	Count	10	4	14	0.1961	0.6578
	% within GROUPS	16.9%	13.3%	15.7%		

The p-value of 0.6578 indicates a no statistically significant association between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of mild findings on ultrasound.

TABLE 14: CORRELATION OF THIN SEPTATIONS ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA

Total Thin septations findings in the study were 28

Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 27 and 1 respectively.

Causes of exudative pleural effusion-

- Malignancy - 2
- Empyema- 8
- Parapneumonic- 5
- TB-12

Causes of transudative pleural effusion-

- CLD-1

SEPTATIONS		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			
Thin	Count	27	1	28	16.604	0.001

	% within GROUPS	96.43%	3.57%	100%		
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The p-value of 0.001 indicates a statistically significant association between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of thin septations.

TABLE 15: CORRELATION OF THICK SEPTATIONS ON ULTRASOUND THORAX WITH LIGHTS CRITERIA

Total thick septations findings in the study were 7

Divided into exudative and transudative groups which were 7 and 0 respectively.

Causes of exudative pleural effusion- Malignancy - 1

TB- 1

Parapneumonic-2

Empyema- 3

SEPTATIONS		LIGHTS CRITERIA		Total	Chi square test	Significant value
		Exudative	Transudative			
Thick	Count	7	0	7	3.863	0.0494
	% within GROUPS	100%	0	100%		

The p-value of 0.0494 indicates a statistically significant association between the type of PE (exudative vs. transudative) and the presence of thick septations.

TABLE 16: IMPACT OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS ON MANAGEMENT OF PLEURAL EFFUSION

The cases in our study were managed with the procedures - Thoracocentesis, ICD tube drainage and Decortication as depicted in the below table.

ULTRASOUND THORAX	CONSERVATIVE MANAGEMENT THERAPEUTIC PLEURAL ASPIRATION	SURGICAL MANAGEMENT ICD TUBE INSERTION UNDERWATER SEAL	SURGICAL MANAGEMENT THORACOTOMY/ VATS DECORTICATIONS
Massive effusion with no septations and loculation	13	1	-
Moderate effusion with no septations and loculations	10	-	-
Minimal Effusion	14	-	-
Effusion with heterogenous internal echoes	3	13	-
Effusion with homogenous internal echoes	-	2	-
Effusion with thin internal septations	-	26	-
Effusion with thick internal septations	-	-	6
Effusion with a single locule	-	-	-
Effusion with multiple locules	-	-	1

- 13 Cases with Gross pleural effusions with no septations and loculations were intended to be managed with ICD tube insertion, but they were instead handled with Therapeutic pleural aspiration because
 - In patients who were critically ill and unstable hemodynamics that made invasive procedure risky, therapeutic pleural aspiration was preferred.
 - Some patients preferred a less invasive procedure, when they were informed about the differences between the two methods and the potential outcomes.

- In patients who were having comorbidities, therapeutic pleural aspiration was preferred.
 - Therapeutic pleural aspiration was chosen in few cases more cost-effective and resource-efficient option.
- Cases with Thin septations [2 cases] and homogenously echogenic pleural effusion [1 case] were intended to be managed with ICD tube insertion, but they are instead handled with Therapeutic pleural aspiration since they appeared to be mild cases.

Graph 15: ROC CURVE ANALYSIS OF PROCALCITONIN LEVELS VALUES:

Case Processing Summary	
LIGHTS CRITERIA	Valid N (listwise)
Positive	59
Negative	30
Larger values of the test result variable(s) indicate stronger evidence for a positive actual state.	

Area Under the Curve			
Test Result Variable(s): Concentration pg/ml			
Area	Std. Error ^a	Asymptotic Sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval

			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
.989	.010	.000	.969	1.000
a. Under the nonparametric assumption				
b. Null hypothesis: true area = 0.5				

Cutoff value- 345.45 pg/ml

- Sensitivity:** 96.6% (0.966)
- Specificity:** 96.8% (0.968)

➤ At the point of highest sensitivity and specificity, cutoff value was taken as 345.45pg/ml [0.345ng/ml] in this study

Table 17: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO PROCALCITONIN IN PLEURAL FLUID LEVELS [pg/ml and ng/ml]

Of 89 patients, 35.96% had a procalcitonin level in pleural fluid equal to less than 345.45pg/ml [0.345ng/ml] whereas 64.04% had a procalcitonin level in pleural fluid level ng/ml more than 345.45pg/ml [0.345ng/ml].

PROCALCITONIN	COUNT	PERCENTAGE
≤345.45pg/ml	32	35.96%
>345.45pg/ml	57	64.04%

Table 18: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES OF PLEURAL EFFUSION CASES WITH PROCALCITONIN LEVELS (<345.45pg/ml) IN PLEURAL FLUID

The distribution of etiologies of cases with procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid which were less than 345.45 pg/ml [0.345ng/ml] included as given in the below table

PROCALCITONIN pg/ml	CAUSES
250-300 pg/ml	1 CKD
301-345.45 pg/ml	1TB 8 CKD

	11CLD 11 HF
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Table 19: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES OF PLEURAL EFFUSION CASES WITH PROCALCITONIN LEVELS (≥ 345.45 pg/ml) IN PLEURAL FLUID

The distribution of etiologies of cases with procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid which were more than or equal to 345.45 pg/ml[0.345ng/ml]. included as given in the below table

PROCALCITONIN pg/ml	CAUSES
345.45-1000 pg/ml	1 PE 8 malignancy 10 parapneumonic 23 TB
1001-3000 pg/ml	1 TB 1 parapneumonic 1 malignancy 1 empyema
3001-5000 pg/ml	1 empyema 1 parapneumonic
>5000 pg/ml	9 empyema

TABLE 20: STATISTICAL DATA OF PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [pg/ml] IN PLEURAL FLUID IN EXUDATIVE GROUP

The Mean \pm SD of the Exudative group in our study was found to be 9.67 \pm 25.8ng/ml.

EXUDATIVE GROUP

Procalcitonin pg/ml		
N	Valid	59
	Missing	0
Mean		9674.3
Median		495.61
Std. Deviation		25838.5
Minimum		318.57
Maximum		97513.1
Percentiles	25	397.74
	50	495.61
	75	1005.80

TABLE 21: STATISTICAL DATA OF PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [pg/ml] IN PLEURAL FLUID IN TRANSUDATIVE GROUP

The Mean± SD of the Transudative group in our study was found to be 0.32±0.01ng/ml.

TRANSUDATIVE GROUP

Procalcitonin pg/ml		
N	Valid	30
	Missing	0
Mean		320.29
Median		321.05
Std. Deviation		11.67
Minimum		295.41
Maximum		341.78
Percentiles	25	310.41
	50	321.05
	75	329.76

TABLE 22: CORRELATION BETWEEN EXUDATIVE EFFUSION AND TRANSUDATIVE EFFUSION CASES REGARDING PROCALCITONIN LEVELS IN PLEURAL FLUID [pg/ml]

The correlation between the procalcitonin levels in exudative effusion cases and transudative effusion cases was given in the below table using Mann- whitney test.

	LIGHTS CRITERIA	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
PROCALCITONIN [pg/ml]	Exudative	59	9674.36	25838.590
	Transudative	30	320.29	11.675

	PROCALCITONIN
Mann-Whitney U	17.000
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.0001

The Mann-Whitney U test results indicated a statistically **significant difference** in Procalcitonin levels between the Exudative and Transudative groups ($p = 0.0001$).

Table 23: STATISTICAL COMPARISON OF PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [PG/ML] WITHIN THE TRANSUDATIVE GROUP

The correlation of the procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid within the transudative effusion groups were analyzed in the below table

TRANSUDATIVE GROUP							
Procalcitonin Concentration [pg/ml]							
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
CLD	10	323.8043	11.66012	315.4631	332.1454	304.90	339.37
CKD	9	315.4028	14.62725	304.1593	326.6463	295.42	341.79
HF	11	321.0943	8.19696	315.5875	326.6011	306.68	330.73
Total	30	320.2901	11.67485	315.9307	324.6496	295.42	341.79

Test Statistics	
	Concentration pg/ml
Kruskal-Wallis H	2.436
Asymp. Sig.	0.296

There is no statistically significant difference in Procalcitonin concentrations among the CLD, CKD, and HF groups within the Transudative category.

Table 24: STATISTICAL COMPARISON OF PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [PG/ML] WITHIN THE EXUDATIVE GROUP

The correlation of the procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid within the transudative effusion groups were analyzed in the below table

		MALIGNANY	PPE	PE	TB	EMPYEMA
Mean		593.64	889.23	344.89	505.81	49220.8
Median		506.61	546.08	344.89	425.62	74080.1
Std. Deviation		217.75	951.98	-	206.01	41909.9
Minimum		388.11	354.13	344.89	318.57	1230.87
Maximum		1076.30	3804.23	344.89	1155.46	97513.09
Percentiles	25	453.24	398.60	344.89	6532.31	6532.31
	50	506.61	546.08	344.89	9223.37	9223.37

Table 25: STATISTICAL COMPARISON BETWEEN EMPYEMA AND NON-EMPYEMA CASES REGARDING PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [PG/ML] IN PLEURAL FLUID

The Mean± SD of the empyema group in our study was found to be 49.2±41.9ng/ml.

EMPYEMA				
	Empyema	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Concentration of procalcitonin pg/ml	0	78	466.5773	222.50723
	1	11	49254.8062	41921.43019

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test Summary	
Total N	89
Mann-Whitney U	857.000
Wilcoxon W	923.000
Test Statistic	857.000
Standard Error	80.218
Standardized Test Statistic	5.335

Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.000
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The Mann-Whitney U test indicates a **significant difference** in Concentration pg/ml between the Empyema and non-Empyema groups ($p < 0.001$).

Table 26 : STATISTICAL COMPARISON BETWEEN TUBERCULOUS AND NON-TUBERCULOUS CASES REGARDING PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [PG/ML] IN PLEURAL FLUID

The Mean \pm SD of the tuberculosis group in our study was found to be 0.50 \pm 0.20ng/ml.

TUBERCULOSIS				
	TB	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Concentration of procalcitonin pg/ml	1	25	505.81	206.011
	0	64	8871.10	9223.37

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test Summary	
Total N	89
Mann-Whitney U	951.000
Wilcoxon W	1276.000
Test Statistic	951.000
Standard Error	109.545
Standardized Test Statistic	1.378
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.168

The Mann-Whitney U test indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in Concentration pg/ml between the TB and non-TB groups ($p = 0.168$)

Table 27: STATISTICAL COMPARISON BETWEEN MALIGNANCY AND NON-MALIGNANT CASES REGARDING PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [PG/ML] IN PLEURAL FLUID

The Mean \pm SD of the Malignancy group in our study was found to be 0.59 \pm 0.21ng/ml.

Malignancy					
	Malignancy	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Concentration of procalcitonin pg/ml	1	9	593.64	217.75	72.58
	0	80	7188.16	9223.37	2519.25

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test Summary	
Total N	89
Mann-Whitney U	498.000
Wilcoxon W	543.000
Test Statistic	498.000
Standard Error	73.485
Standardized Test Statistic	1.878
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.060

The Mann-Whitney U test indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in Concentration pg/ml between the Malignancy and non-Malignancy groups (p = 0.060).

Table 28: STATISTICAL COMPARISON BETWEEN PARAPNEUMONIC AND NON- PARAPNEUMONIC CASES REGARDING PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [PG/ML] IN PLEURAL FLUID

The Mean± SD of the parapneumonic group in our study was found to be 0.88±0.95ng/ml.

Parapneumonic effusion				
	Parapneumonic	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Concentration of procalcitonin pg/ml	1	12	889.23	951.98
	0	77	7399.026	9223.37

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test Summary	
Total N	89
Mann-Whitney U	637.000
Wilcoxon W	715.000
Test Statistic	637.000
Standard Error	83.247
Standardized Test Statistic	2.102
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.036

The Mann-Whitney U test indicates a **statistically significant difference** in Concentration pg/ml between the Parapneumonic and non-Parapneumonic groups (p = 0.036).

Table 29: STATISTICAL COMPARISON BETWEEN PULMONARY EMBOLISM AND NON- PULMONARY EMBOLISM CASES REGARDING PROCALCITONIN LEVELS [PG/ML] IN PLEURAL FLUID

The Mean_of the pulmonary thromboembolism group in our study was found to be 0.34ng/ml.

Pulmonary thromboembolism					
	PE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Concentration of procalcitonin pg/ml	1	1	344.89	.	.
	0	88	6591.48	9223.37	2297.84

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test Summary	
Total N	89
Mann-Whitney U	31.000
Wilcoxon W	32.000
Test Statistic	31.000
Standard Error	25.690
Standardized Test Statistic	-.506
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.613
Exact Sig.(2-sided test)	.719

The Mann-Whitney U test indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in Concentration pg/ml between the Pulmonary Embolism (PE) and non-PE groups ($p = 0.719$)

DISCUSSION

Thoracic ultrasonography has emerged as a pivotal tool in the medical field, providing critical insights into the characteristics of pleural effusion, thereby enhancing diagnostic accuracy and guiding effective clinical management. The ability to predict the chemical traits of pleural effusion into transudative and exudative effusions prior to sampling may impact subsequent management and potentially decrease the need for invasive procedures like thoracentesis and the associated procedural risks.

AGE AND GENDER DISTRIBUTION:

The age of the patients in the transudative effusion and exudative effusion groups being studied ranged from 18 years to 85 years & the mean age was 50.8 ± 18.1 years

Mean \pm SD of age in Studies	Transudative group	Exudative group
Al-Aarag AH et al., ¹⁰² 2020	58 \pm 6.8 years	53 \pm 6.5 years
C.-Y Wang et al., ¹⁰³ 2010	74.1 \pm 5 years	65.4 \pm 2.5 years
Ahmed MI, et al., ¹⁰⁵ 2024	48.5(20-69 years)	56(18-90 years)
Bandaru RC et al., ¹⁰⁴ 2018	49.5 (22-77 years)	58 (18-98 years)
Our study	53.8 \pm 14.2 years	49.3 \pm 19.6 years

The distribution of age groups comparing to other studies was depicted in the above table. In the transudative group, their ages were between 21 and 80 years with a mean \pm SD of 53.8 \pm 14.2 years and in the exudative group their ages were between 18 and 85 years with a mean \pm SD of 49.3 \pm 19.6 years. The mean \pm SD in the studies done by, Al-Aarag AH et al.,¹⁰² 2020, C.-Y Wang et al.,¹⁰³ 2010, Ahmed MI, et al.,¹⁰⁵2024, Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 showed correlation with our study.

The transudative group included 19 (63.3%) males and 11 (36.6%) females. The exudative group included 42 (71.2%) males and 17(28.8%) females. Male preponderance was seen in our study which correlated with Evans PT study et al.,⁹⁴ 2021, El Wahsh et al.,¹⁰⁶, 2022, Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 and Ahmed MI, et al.,¹⁰⁵2024 studies which showed gender inclination was towards males (58.5%), (64%), (65%) and (63.3%) respectively as showed in the below table which could be attributed to the higher smoking rates or exposure to environmental pollutants.

STUDIES	MALE GENDER (%)	FEMALE GENDER (%)
Evans PT study et al., ⁹⁴ 2021	58.5%	41.5%
El Wahsh et al., ¹⁰⁶ , 2022,	64%	36%
Bandaru RC et al., ¹⁰⁴ 2018	65%	35%
Ahmed MI, et al., ¹⁰⁵ 2024	63.3%	36.7%

Our study	68.5%	31.5%
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In this study, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups which indicated that the age and sex of our groups were well matched.

ASSESSMENT OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS:

32 patients (35.96%) with pleural effusion had anechoogenic finding, while 19 patients (21.35%) had complex non-septate finding, and 35 patients (39.33%) had complex septate finding and 3 (3.36%) patients had homogenous echoes finding as depicted in graph 1.

USG THORAX FINDINGS (%) IN STUDIES	ANECHOGENIC FINDING	COMPLEX NON-SEPTATE FINDING	COMPLEX SEPTATE FINDING	HOMOGENOUS ECHOES FINDING
Bandaru RC et al., ¹⁰⁴ 2018	33.7%	17.5%	42.5%	6.2%
Wang et al., ⁹⁷ 2022	71.5%	17.2%	8.1%	3.3%
Evans PT study et al., ⁹⁴ 2021	71%	17.4%	10.8%	0.7%
Ahmed MI, et al., ¹⁰⁵ 2024	25%	8.3%	51.6%	56%
Our study	35.96%	21.35%	39.33%	3.36%

These results were in accordance with the study conducted by Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 as showed in the above table although the percentages varied from our study. The findings in the study by Ahmed MI, et al.,¹⁰⁵ 2024, reported complex septate finding predominance (51.6%) which correlated with our study while Wang et al.,⁹⁷ 2022 and Evans PT study et al.,⁹⁴ 2021 studies showed higher number of anechogenic finding (71.5%) and (71%) respectively as shown in the above table which contrasted with our study results. Wide variations in the ultrasonography findings data indicated above were observed in several studies on patients with pleural effusions.

It was observed that the complex septate finding was the most common ultrasonography finding in these pleural effusion cases in our study. The results of our study were consistent with the study conducted by Ahmed MI, et al.,¹⁰⁵ 2024 and Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 where complex septate finding was predominant 67.3% and 42.5% respectively as showed in the below table, though the percentages of distribution of cases varied.

STUDIES	COMPLEX SEPTATE FINDING IN USG
Bandaru RC et al., ¹⁰⁴ 2018	42.5%
Ahmed MI, et al., ¹⁰⁵ 2024	51.6%
Our study	39.3%

Ultrasound is more sensitive in detecting septations in the pleural fluid when compared to other radiological investigations.⁹ Septae can be explained by activation of the coagulation cascade, resulting in deposition of fibrin.

Among the complex septate pleural effusions in our study, thin septations were predominantly 28 (80%) followed by thick septations which were 7 (20%) as showed in

graph 2. These results are similar to a study by El Wahsh et al.,¹⁰⁶ 2022 which reported thick septations in only 10% cases.

ASSESSMENT OF QUANTITY ON ULTRASOUND THORAX:

In the present study, it was observed that 21 patients (23.6%) had gross pleural effusion, while 54 patients (60.7%) had moderate pleural effusion, and 14 patients (15.7%) were diagnosed with mild pleural effusion as depicted in graph 3.

These results are similar to a study conducted by El Wahsh et al.,¹⁰⁶ 2022 where patients with moderate pleural effusion were predominant (54%) followed by those with gross pleural effusion (17%), while patients with mild pleural effusion were least in number (15%). In Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 study moderate effusions were higher (51.2%) and in contrary to our results mild and moderate effusions were (27.5%) and (21.2) respectively as showed in the below table

STUDIES	GROSS PE	MODERATE PE	MILD PE
El Wahsh et al., ¹⁰⁶ 2022	17%	54%	15%
Bandaru RC et al., ¹⁰⁴ 2018	21.2	51.2%	27.5%
Our study	23.6%	60.7%	15.7%

ASSESSMENT OF SITE OF EFFUSION ON ULTRASOUND THORAX:

49 patients (55%) in the current study were found to have right-sided pleural effusions, 25 patients (28.1%) had left-sided pleural effusions, and 15 patients

(16.9%) had bilateral pleural effusions as showed in graph 4. These results are in accordance to the study conducted by Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 most of the pleural effusions were unilateral (66.7%) and more common on right side (75.4%). Contrast to our study results, El Wahsh et al.,¹⁰⁶ 2022 showed left sided effusion predominance (17%).

ASSESSMENT OF THICKENED PLEURA ON ULTRASOUND THORAX:

16 (17.9%) patients of exudative pleural effusions had thickened pleura as showed in graph 5 which correlated with Yang et al.,¹⁰⁷ study, which observed that thickened pleura and lung parenchymal changes are indicative of exudates. A study by Helala et al.,⁹⁹ 2015, reported that ultrasonography thorax had better accuracy in detecting pleural thickening. Most of the thickened pleura findings were seen in empyema cases in our study which correlated with the El Wahsh et al.,¹⁰⁶ 2022 study findings. According to Wang et al.,⁹⁷ 2022 in contrary to the results of our study, majority of thickened pleura seen in the tuberculosis group which could result from a greater number of TB cases in the study.

CORRELATION OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS WITH LIGHTS

CRITERIA:

1. Correlation of Anechogenic finding on ultrasound thorax with Lights criteria:

In our study among 32 patients with anechogenic findings in ultrasonography, 9 (15.3%) patients had exudative pleural effusions, whereas 23 (76.7%) patients had transudative pleural effusions. There was a positive and **statistically significant** ($P < 0.05$) correlation between anechogenic findings on ultrasound and the type of pleural effusion defined by Light's criteria as depicted in table 1&7. These results are in accordance

to the study conducted by et al., Yang et al.,¹⁰⁷ study in which all patients with transudates presented with anechogenic appearance on ultrasonography (96/96) and anechogenic effusion could be a transudative or exudative (33.6%). Study by Wang et al.,⁹⁷ 2022 also reported that in 416 anechogenic findings, 40% patients had exudative pleural effusions, whereas (99.7%) patients had transudative pleural effusions and had a positive and statistically significant (P<0.05) correlation. Comparable to our study, Ahmed MI, et al.,¹⁰⁵2024 and Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 also reported that statistically significant (P<0.05) correlation was seen between the percentage of patients with exudative pleural effusions (2.17%) (3.5%) and transudative pleural effusions (100%) (100%) respectively as showed in below table. The frequency of appearance of anechogenic finding in ultrasonography was higher in patients with heart failure patients in our study which correlated with Wang et al.,⁹⁷ 2022 study in which pleural effusion patients with heart failure had a higher frequency of anechogenic findings on ultrasonography.

ANECHOGENIC FINDING IN STUDIES	EXUDATIVE PE	TRANSUDATIVE PE
Yang et al., ¹⁰⁷ study	33%	100%
Wang et al., ⁹⁷ 2022	40%	99.7%
Ahmed MI, et al., ¹⁰⁵ 2024	2.17%	100%
Bandaru RC et al., ¹⁰⁴ 2018	3.5%	100%
Our study	15.3%	76.7%

2. Correlation of Complex septate finding on ultrasound thorax with Lights

criteria:

The data in our study showed a strong association between complex septate findings on ultrasound thorax and exudative pleural effusions, with 34(57.6%) of

exudative cases displaying complex septate characteristics compared to only 1(3.3%) of transudative cases. The p-value of <0.05 indicates this association is **statistically significant** as depicted in table 1 & 8. This is consistent with Ahmed MI, et al.,¹⁰⁵2024 and Soni et al.,⁴⁸ 2015 study and Brogi et al.,¹⁰⁸ 2017 study which also reported significant positive correlation association between complex septate findings on ultrasound and exudative pleural effusions. In our study, complex septate finding was more commonly observed in TB (13) and empyema (11) which correlated with Wang et al.,⁹⁷ 2022 study which showed Empyema predominance.

3. Correlation of Complex non septate finding on ultrasound thorax with Lights criteria:

Out of 19 patients with non-septate findings, 13 (22%) patients had exudative pleural effusions, whereas 6 (20%) patients had transudative pleural effusions. The percentage of complex non-septate effusions is slightly higher in the exudative group compared to the transudative group but there is no significant difference in the occurrence of complex non-septate USG findings between exudative and transudative pleural effusions as in table 1 & 9. Comparable to our study, Evans PT study et al.,⁹⁴ 2021 stated that there was no statistically significant ($P<0.05$) correlation between nonseptate findings on ultrasound and the type of pleural effusion defined by Light's criteria and not sensitive for exudative or transudative fluids. In contrast to our study Wang et al.,⁹⁷ 2022 and Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 reported that non-septate ultrasonography findings were not present in any transudative effusion patients. These contradictory results could be attributed to the different stages of some primary diseases in studies. Complex non-septate findings were more frequently seen in TB cases (8) in our study.

4. Correlation of Homogenous echoes finding on ultrasound thorax with Lights

criteria:

The data in our study showed that homogenous echoes are observed only in exudative pleural effusions (5.1%) and not in transudative effusions. However, the p-value of 0.209 indicates that this association is not statistically significant as in table 1 & 10. The small numbers involved make it difficult to achieve significance due to low statistical power. Homogeneously echogenic effusions tend to occur with hemorrhagic effusions or high content of tissue debris and are most often exudative as stated in by Soni et al.,⁴⁹ 2015 and Brogi et al.,¹⁰⁸ 2017 study. The appearances were seen in 2 TB and 1 parapneumonic effusion cases which opposed with the results of Wang et al.,⁹⁷ 2022 study in which malignant cases predominance was seen and the discrepancy could be due to the higher number of hemorrhagic effusions in the malignant cases.

5. Correlation of Quantity and Site on ultrasound thorax with Lights criteria:

Out of 89 pleural effusions in the gross category, the proportion of transudative cases is higher (50%), while in the moderate category, exudative cases are more prevalent (72.9%) with statistically significant correlation as depicted in tables (11-13). Comparable to our study Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 study also reported moderate effusions predominance in exudative group and in contrary to our findings, gross effusions were also more in the same group.

Among the 89 cases, most of the pleural effusions were unilateral (83.1%) and more common on right side (55 %). Bilateral effusions are more common in transudative group (26.7%) compared to exudative group (11.9%) as showed in table 4 which

is in accordance with the Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018 study which showed transudative effusions were more often bilateral (87.5%) in comparison to exudative effusions which were unilateral (89.2%) with a statistically significant value although the percentages differed.

Most of the exudative effusions in our study were complex septated (39.3%), echogenic (3.3%) or complex non-septated (21.3%) on ultrasound with few being anechoic (35.9%). Transudative effusions were mostly anechoic (76.7%) in our study, as depicted in the table 1, which correlated with the other studies by Bandaru RC et al.,¹⁰⁴ 2018, Dr Ahmed MI, et al.,¹⁰⁵ 2024 and Brogi et al.,¹⁰⁸ 2017 which reported that anechogenic findings in ultrasonography thorax were more likely transudates and complex septate and internal echogenicity indicated exudates.

This study highlights the utility of ultrasonography findings in distinguishing between exudative and transudative pleural effusions. Anechogenic findings were more common in transudative effusions but can also be present in exudative ones. Complex septate findings are significantly associated with exudative effusions. Complex non-septate findings do not significantly differ between exudative and transudative effusions, and homogeneous echoes are associated with exudative effusions and did not show a significant correlation with either type of effusion. These insights can aid in the non-invasive differentiation of pleural effusions, guiding further diagnostic and therapeutic approaches.

IMPACT OF ULTRASOUND THORAX FINDINGS ON MANAGEMENT OF PLEURAL EFFUSION

Ultrasound thorax findings help in the management of pleural effusion by providing real-time imaging for effective intervention. It can be used in the evaluation of various characteristics and size of the effusions. The echogenicity of the

effusion should be noted, which gives an indication to its aetiology. Effusions either due to infection or malignancy tend to form fibrous septations which, if present, have various diagnostic and therapeutic implications. The parietal and visceral pleurae should be inspected for thickening or nodularity.

Pleural aspiration is required to determine the nature of any effusion and in cases of simple pleural effusions and chest tube insertions will be needed in complex pleural effusion cases. As per the BTS guidelines, both procedures should be done with the guidance of Thoracic ultrasonography to ensure a successful and safe procedure.⁴⁶

Among the 14 cases with massive effusion with no septations and loculations in our study, 13 cases were managed effectively with therapeutic pleural aspiration as depicted in table 16. ICD tube insertion was done in one case. Thoracocentesis was performed rather than tube insertion in these gross simple effusion cases owing to the conditions of unstable hemodynamics, comorbidities, cost-effectiveness, choice of the patient.

All the 10 cases with moderate effusion with no septations and loculations in this study were managed successfully with therapeutic pleural aspiration as depicted in table 16. Moderate effusions can often be were typically straightforward to aspirate and resolved with aspiration, especially in the absence of complicating factors like septations or loculations.

In this study therapeutic pleural aspiration was performed in all 14 cases of minimal effusions as showed in table 16. Mild effusions were typically managed conservatively, and aspiration was usually sufficient for symptomatic relief or diagnostic purposes.

In cases of pleural effusion with heterogeneous internal echoes, therapeutic pleural aspiration was performed in 3 cases and ICD tube insertion was done in 13 cases as depicted in table 16. The presence of heterogeneous internal echoes often indicates complex effusions, possibly due to infection or malignancy, necessitating more aggressive management with ICD tubes to ensure adequate drainage and prevent complications.⁹ Shankar *et al*¹¹⁵ study found that a complex septated parapneumonic effusion had a 62.5% resolution rate with chest tube drainage compared with 81.5% with a complex non-septated parapneumonic effusion.

ICD tube insertion was performed in 2 cases effusions with homogeneous internal echoes as showed in table 16. Tube insertion was generally preferred over pleural aspiration, as homogeneous echoes often indicated a more complex and uniform fluid which required continuous drainage.

All the 26 cases with thin internal septations, ICD tube insertion was performed as depicted in table 16. Thin septations can compartmentalize the effusion, making simple aspiration ineffective and requiring the use of ICD tubes to ensure thorough drainage. Extensive septations can complicate the management of pleural infection by impeding thorough drainage and may be predictors of failed medical treatment and the need for management escalation. In these septated effusions, real-time TUS guidance can be used to direct chest drain placement into the largest locule visualised.⁹ Two studies Silverman SG *et al.*,¹¹⁷ and Shankar S *et al.*,¹¹⁵ have demonstrated the utility of ultrasound-guided chest drainage as the principal treatment for parapneumonic effusion or empyema with an overall success rate of 78% and 72% respectively. Chen *et al*¹¹⁶ showed that sonographically visible septations were associated with a longer hospital stay, longer chest tube drainage, higher likelihood of fibrinolytic therapy and surgical intervention.

In this study, 6 effusion cases with thick internal septations were managed with thoracotomy/VATS as described in table 16. Thick septations are indicative of a more organized and potentially fibrotic process, often necessitating surgical intervention to break down the septations and ensure complete drainage.⁴⁸ The formation of adhesions was preceded by fibrinous septations being infiltrated by fibroblasts over course of time followed by collagen deposition and decortication procedures were considered as choice of management.¹⁰⁶

Effusion with multiple locules was managed with VATS in one case in our study as depicted in table 16. Multiple loculated effusions were complex and challenging to manage with aspiration or ICD tubes alone, often require surgical intervention to address effectively.⁹

The management strategies for pleural effusions varied significantly based on the ultrasound characteristics of the effusions. Simple effusions without septations and loculations were mostly managed with therapeutic aspiration, while complex effusions, particularly those with thin septations or loculations, and with heterogenous or homogenous echoes often necessitated ICD tube insertion and those with thick septations or multiple loculations required more invasive procedures like thoracotomy/VATS. Ultrasound findings play a crucial role in guiding these decisions, ensuring appropriate and effective treatment tailored to the specific characteristics of each effusion

CORRELATION OF PLEURAL FLUID PROCALCITONIN LEVELS WITH LIGHTS

CRITERIA:

Procalcitonin (PCT) is a potential indicator of systemic inflammation due to infection. PCT has been investigated in this study to recognize its role in correlation with lights criteria and in the diagnosis of different etiologies of exudative and transudative pleural effusion, thereby enhancing clinical decision-making and optimizing patient management strategies.

PROCALCITONIN VALUES IN PLEURAL FLUID (ng/ml)							
Author & year	Transudative Effusions (ng/ml)	Exudative effusions (ng/ml)	Empyema (ng/ml)	Tuberculous effusions (ng/ml)	Malignant Effusions (ng/ml)	PE (ng/ml)	PPE (ng/ml)
Al-Aarag AH et al., ¹⁰² 2020	0.186 ± 0.063	1.387 ± 1.566	-	0.262 ± 0.171	0.500 ± 0.239	-	3.400 ± 4.672
C.-Y Wang et al., ¹⁰³ 2010	0.188 ± 0.077	-	5.147 ± 3.056	0.130 ± 0.069	0.241 ± 0.071	-	1.091 ± 0.355
Sharma et al., ¹¹⁸ 2021	-	-	27.14 ± 23.8	3.078 ± 2.623	1.174 ± 1.542	-	
Kocer et al., ¹¹³ 2012	0.08 ± 0.05	-		0.13 ± 0.16	0.16 ± 0.29	-	0.11 ± 0.22
El-Shimy WS et al., ¹¹⁴ 2014	0.169 ± 0.074	-	-	0.204 ± 0.033	0.636 ± 0.167	-	1.760 ± 0.312

Bülent Akkurt et al.,2020 ¹⁰¹	0.47±1.45						0.90±2.93
In our study	0.32 ± 0.01	9.67± 25.8	49.2 ±41.9	0.50 ± 0.20	0.59 ± 0.21	0.344	0.88 ± 0.95

PPE- parapneumonic effusion PE- pulmonary thromboembolic effusion

The mean ± SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid in transudative pleural effusion group in this study was 0.32 ± 0.01 ng/ml and exudative pleural effusion was 9.67± 25.8 ng/ml with **statistically significant (P<0.05)** value as showed in the above table and table 20 - 22 which is higher compared to a study done by Al-Aarag AH et al.,¹⁰² 2020, mean ±SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid of transudative group was 0.186±0.063 ng/ml and exudative group was 1.387±1.566 ng/ml which is statistically significant (P<0.0001).

Among transudative effusions, there is no statistically significant difference in procalcitonin concentrations among the CLD, CKD, and HF groups. The similar range and overlapping confidence intervals across the groups further support the conclusion that PCT levels are relatively consistent regardless of the underlying condition as showed in the table 23.

Among exudative effusions, our study found that the mean ±SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid was significantly higher in Empyema group which was 49.2 ± 41.9 ng/ml compared to other groups, which were parapneumonic group with mean ±SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid 0.88 ± 0.95 ng/ml, malignancy group with mean ±SD of 0.59 ± 0.21 ng/ml, Tuberculous group with mean ±SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid of 0.50 ±

0.20ng/ml as showed in table 24. These findings highlight the potential of using PCT levels as a diagnostic marker to differentiate empyema and parapneumonic effusions from other types of pleural effusions.

One case reported with pulmonary thromboembolism had a value of 0.344 ng/ml. (table 29)

The mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid the empyema group in our study showed more elevated values than other studies like Sharma et al.,¹¹⁸ 2021, C.-Y Wang et al.,¹⁰³ 2010, which reported values of (27.1 \pm 23.8 ng/ml) and (5.147 \pm 3.05 ng/ml) respectively. More severe infections typically can result in higher systemic inflammatory responses and comorbid conditions can reflect elevated PCT levels. High **statistically significant difference** in Concentration pg/ml between the empyema and non-empyema groups in our study as depicted in table 25.

Author & year	Procalcitonin in Empyema (ng/ml)
C.-Y Wang et al., ¹⁰³ 2010	5.147 \pm 3.056
Sharma et al., ¹¹⁸ 2021	27.1 \pm 23.8
In our study	49.2 \pm 41.9

In contrary to the results of our study, Al-Aarag AH et al.,¹⁰² 2020, C.-Y Wang et al.,¹⁰³ 2010, Bülent Akkurt et al.,²⁰²⁰¹⁰¹, El-Shimy WS et al¹¹⁴., 2014 studies reported a significantly higher mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid (3.40 \pm 1.02 ng/ml) (1.09 \pm 0.35 ng/ml) (0.90 \pm 2.93ng/ml) (1.760 \pm 0.312ng/ml) respectively in parapneumonic effusions. There is evidence that pleural fluid PCT lacks the ability of separating complicated parapneumonic effusions from uncomplicated ones which can explain the results of our study.¹¹⁰ A **statistically significant** difference in Concentration of

procalcitonin (ng/ml) between the parapneumonic and non-parapneumonic groups (p = 0.036) in our study as showed in table 28.

Author & year	Procalcitonin in PPE (ng/ml)
Al-Aarag AH et al., ¹⁰² 2020	3.400 ± 4.672
C.-Y Wang et al., ¹⁰³ 2010	1.091± 0.355
Kocer et al., ¹¹³ 2012	0.11±0.22
El-Shimy WS et al., ¹¹⁴ 2014	1.760 ± 0.312
Bülent Akkurt et al.,2020 ¹⁰¹	0.90±2.93
In our study	0.88 ± 0.95

When compared to our study, the mean ±SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid tubercular effusion in Al-Aarag AH et al.,¹⁰² 2020, C.-Y Wang et al.,¹⁰³ 2010, El-Shimy WS et al.,¹¹⁴ 2014 and Sharma et al.,¹¹²2021 had (0.262±0.171), (0.130 ± 0.069) (0.204 ± 0.0330) (3.078 ±2.623) respectively which reported low PCT levels, can be possibly due to differences in TB severity or sample variability. Table 26 depicted that there is no statistically significant difference in Concentration pg/ml between the TB and nonTB groups (p = 0.168) in our study.

Author & year	Procalcitonin in Tuberculous effusions (ng/ml)
Al-Aarag AH et al., ¹⁰² 2020	0.262 ± 0.171
C.-Y Wang et al., ¹⁰³ 2010	0.130 ±0.069
Sharma et al., ¹¹² 2021	3.078 ±2.623
El-Shimy WS et al., ¹¹⁴ 2014	0.204 ± 0.033
In our study	0.50 ± 0.20

The mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid in malignant effusion in Al-Aarag AH et al.,¹⁰² 2020, C.-Y Wang et al.,¹⁰³ 2010, studies were (0.500 \pm 0.239), (0.241 \pm 0.071) which were slightly lower than our study. Higher levels of tumor necrosis can release more inflammatory mediators, including PCT which can be observed in our study. El-Shimy WS et al.,¹¹⁴ 2014, Sharma et al.,¹¹²2021 had mean \pm SD of (0.636 \pm 0.167) (1.174 \pm 1.542) which were higher than our study. Table 27 showed that there is no statistically significant difference in Concentration pg/ml between the Malignancy and non-Malignancy groups (p = 0.060).

Author & year	Procalcitonin in Malignant effusions(ng/ml)
Al-Aarag AH et al., ¹⁰² 2020	0.500 \pm 0.239
Kocer et al., ¹¹³ 2012	0.16 \pm 0.29
C.-Y Wang et al., ¹⁰³ 2010	0.241 \pm 0.071
Sharma et al., ¹¹² 2021	1.174 \pm 1.542
El-Shimy WS et al., ¹¹⁴ 2014	0.636 \pm 0.167
In our study	0.59 \pm 0.21

Comparing the transudative effusions to our study, the mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid, Al-Aarag AH et al.,¹⁰² 2020, C.-Y Wang et al.,¹⁰³ 2010, El-Shimy WS et al.,¹¹⁴ 2014 , Kocer et al.,¹¹³ 2014 showed values of (0.186 \pm 0.063) ,(0.188 \pm 0.077), (0.169 \pm 0.074) (0.08 \pm 0.05) respectively slightly less than our study results.

Author & year	Procalcitonin in Transudative Effusions (ng/ml)
Al-Aarag AH et al., ¹⁰² 2020	0.186 \pm 0.063
C.-Y Wang et al., ¹⁰³ 2010	0.188 \pm 0.077

El-Shimy WS et al., ¹¹⁴ 2014	0.169 ± 0.074
Kocer et al., ¹¹³ 2014	0.08 ± 0.05
In our study	0.32 ± 0.01

We performed ROC analysis to find specific cut-off values to differentiate transudative and exudative levels as showed in graph 16. A procalcitonin level of 345.45 pg/ml (0.345ng.ml) was accepted as the cut-off with the highest sensitivity of 96.6% and specificity of 96.8% as depicted in the graph 15. The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve's area under the curve (AUC) is 0.989

In a study done by Al-Aarag AH et al.,¹⁰² 2020, optimal differentiation between transudative and exudative pleural effusion was achieved at a cutoff value 0.19 ng/ml with area under the curve (AUC) of 0.87 with sensitivity 86% and specificity 54%

Among the 89 patients, 32 patients had procalcitonin level of less than 345.45 pg/ml (0.345 ng/ml) which included all transudates and 57 patients had procalcitonin level of more than or equal to 345.45 pg/ml (0.345 ng/ml) and association between them is **statistically significant** as depicted in tables (19-21). The higher values of procalcitonin was seen in all empyema cases.

In the current study, pleural procalcitonin levels in exudative effusion had significantly higher values when compared with those in transudative one. The results demonstrated the utility of PCT levels as a diagnostic marker to differentiate empyema and parapneumonic effusions from other types of pleural effusions in which high statistical difference seen between the empyema and non-empyema cases. These results could be explained by considering PCT as a potential biomarker of a state or a syndrome (e.g. severe sepsis) rather than an indicator of a disease.¹¹¹

There was a positive correlation between Lights criteria and procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid and the correlation was **statistically significant (P<0.05)**. This indicates that measuring procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid can help differentiate between transudative and exudative effusions, providing an additional diagnostic tool alongside Light's criteria.

LIMITATIONS:

- Small number of cases is included in the study
- Sampling bias may have been present during the thoracentesis procedure which may have influenced the validity of laboratory measurements.
- Interrater reliability during the operation of the ultrasound machine to be considered
- Demographic and baseline patient characteristics have not been analysed.
- Possible influence of treatment cannot be excluded.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of ultrasound thorax as a valuable non-invasive tool for bedside assessment of the nature of the pleural fluid and also essential in guiding the decisions ensuring appropriate and effective treatment tailored to the specific characteristics of each effusion. Anechogenic findings were more common in transudative effusions but can also be present in exudative ones. Complex septate findings are significantly associated with exudative effusions. Complex non-septate findings do not significantly differ between exudative and transudative effusions, and homogeneous echoes are associated with exudative effusions and did not show a significant correlation with either type of effusion. Simple effusions without septations and loculations were mostly managed with therapeutic aspiration, while complex effusions, particularly those with thin septations or loculations, and with heterogeneous or homogeneous echoes often necessitated ICD tube insertion and those with thick septations or multiple loculations required more invasive procedures like thoracotomy/VATS. Measurement of procalcitonin in pleural fluid can be used to differentiate transudative from exudative pleural effusions and can also be used to

differentiate empyema and parapneumonic effusions from other causes of exudative pleural effusions.

SUMMARY:

A cross-sectional study on 89 patients with the diagnosis of pleural effusion, was carried out in the department of Respiratory Medicine OPD/ wards in BLDE[DU] Shri B M Patil medical college, Hospital and Research center, Vijayapura in this study. Ultrasound thorax and Diagnostic Pleural Fluid analysis was done in each patient, and Procalcitonin levels in pleural fluid was measured were measured by ELISA method.

1. Among 89 patients enrolled in this study, the age of the patients being studied ranged from 18 years to 85 years & the mean age was 50.8 ± 18.1 years. In the transudative group, their ages were between 21 and 80 years with a mean \pm SD of 53.8 ± 14.2 years and in the exudative group their ages were between 18 and 85 years with a mean \pm SD of 49.3 ± 19.6 years.
2. Male preponderance was seen in our study with 68.5%.
3. Majority of the cases, 35 patients (39.33%) had complex septate finding in ultrasonography thorax followed by 32 patients (35.96%) with anechogenic finding, while 19 patients (21.35%) had complex non-septate finding, and 35 patients (39.33%) had complex septate finding and 3 (3.36%) patients had homogenous echoes finding.
4. Among the complex septate pleural effusions in our study, thin septations were predominantly 28 (80%) followed by thick septations which were 7 (20%).
5. In the present study, it was observed that 21 patients (23.6%) had gross pleural effusion, while 54 patients (60.7%) had moderate pleural effusion, and 14 patients (15.7%) were diagnosed with mild pleural effusion.

6. 49 patients (55%) in the current study were found to have right-sided pleural effusions, 25 patients (28.1%) had left-sided pleural effusions, and 15 patients (16.9%) had bilateral pleural effusions.
7. 16 (17.9%) patients of exudative pleural effusions had thickened pleura.
8. There was a positive and statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) correlation between anechogenic finding and complex septate finding on ultrasound and the type of pleural effusion defined by Light's criteria.
9. Out of 89 pleural effusions in the gross category, the proportion of transudative cases is higher (50%), while in the moderate category, exudative cases are more prevalent (72.9%) with statistically significant correlation.
10. Among the 89 cases, most of the pleural effusions were unilateral (83.1%) and more common on right side (55 %). Bilateral effusions are more common in transudative group (26.7%) compared to exudative group (11.9%).
11. Most of the exudative effusions in our study were complex septated (39.3%), echogenic (3.3%) or complex non-septated (21.3%) on ultrasound with few being anechoic (35.9%).
12. Transudative effusions were mostly anechoic (76.7%) in our study.
13. Simple effusions without septations and loculations were mostly managed with therapeutic aspiration, while complex effusions, particularly those with thin septations or loculations, and with heterogenous or homogenous echoes often necessitated ICD tube insertion and those with thick septations or multiple loculations required more invasive procedures like thoracotomy/VATS.
14. The mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid in transudative pleural effusion group in this study was 0.32 ± 0.01 ng/ml and exudative pleural effusion was 9.67 ± 25.8 ng/ml (table 19&20) with statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) value.

15. Our study our study found that the mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid was significantly higher in Empyema group which was 49.2 ± 41.9 ng/ml compared to other groups, which were parapneumonic group with mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid 0.88 ± 0.95 ng/ml, malignancy group with mean \pm SD of 0.59 ± 0.21 ng/ml, Tuberculous group with mean \pm SD of procalcitonin in pleural fluid of 0.50 ± 0.20 ng/ml.

16. The results demonstrated the utility of PCT levels as a diagnostic marker to differentiate empyema and parapneumonic effusions from other types of pleural effusions in which high statistical difference seen between the empyema and non-empyema cases.

17. ROC analysis was done to find specific cut-off values to determine transudative and exudative levels. A procalcitonin level of 345.45 pg/ml (0.345ng.ml) was accepted as the cut-off with the highest sensitivity of 96.6% and specificity of 96.8% as depicted in the graph. The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve's area under the curve (AUC) is 0.989.

18. Among the 89 patients, 32 patients had procalcitonin level of less than 345.45 pg/ml (0.345 ng/ml) which included all transudates and 57 patients had procalcitonin level of more than or equal to 345.45 pg/ml (0.345 ng/ml) and association between them is statistically significant.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Jany B, Welte T. Pleural effusion in adults—etiology, diagnosis, and treatment. *Deutsches Ärzteblatt International*. 2019 May;116(21):377.
2. Karkhanis VS, Joshi JM. Pleural effusion: diagnosis, treatment, and management. *Open access emergency medicine*. 2012 Jun 25:31-52.
3. EL-shamly MM, Mohammed EM, Aly MM. Clinical and Thoracoscopic Predictors of Malignant Pleural Effusion. *Al-Azhar International Medical Journal*. 2023;4(11):51.
4. Gupta KB, Aggarwal SK, Sanjay Kumar SK, Manav Manchanda MM. Evaluation of plasma-pleural effusion albumin gradient for differentiating between pleural transudate and exudate.
5. Gázquez I, Porcel JM, Vives M, De Vera MV, Rubio M, Rivas MC. Comparative analysis of Light's criteria and other biochemical parameters for distinguishing transudates from exudates. *Respiratory medicine*. 1998 May 1;92(5):762-5.
6. Burgess LJ, Maritz FJ, Taljaard JF. Comparative analysis of the biochemical parameters used to distinguish between pleural transudates & exudates. *Chest*. 1995 Jun 1;107(6):1604-9
7. Light RW, Macgregor MI, Luchsinger PC, BALL JR WC. Pleural effusions: the diagnostic separation of transudates and exudates. *Annals of internal medicine*. 1972 Oct 1;77(4):507-13.

8. Porcel JM. Identifying transudates misclassified by Light's criteria. *Current opinion in pulmonary medicine*. 2013 Jul 1;19(4):362-7.
9. Hassan M, Mercer RM, Rahman NM. Thoracic ultrasound in the modern management of pleural disease. *European Respiratory Review*. 2020 Jun 30;29(156).
10. Evans PT, Zhang RS, Cao Y, Breslin S, Panebianco N, Baston CM, Dibardino DM. The use of thoracic ultrasound to predict transudative and exudative pleural effusion. *POCUS journal*. 2021;6(2):97.
11. Shkolnik B, Judson MA, Austin A, Hu K, D'Souza M, Zumbrunn A, Huggins JT, Yucel R, Chopra A. Diagnostic accuracy of thoracic ultrasonography to differentiate transudative from exudative pleural effusion. *Chest*. 2020 Aug 1;158(2):692-7.
12. Assicot M, Bohuon C, Gendrel D, Raymond J, Carsin H, Guilbaud JJ. High serum procalcitonin concentrations in patients with sepsis and infection. *The Lancet*. 1993 Feb 27;341(8844):515-8.
13. Wanner GA, Keel M, Steckholzer U, Beier W, Stocker R, Ertel W. Relationship between procalcitonin plasma levels and severity of injury, sepsis, organ failure, and mortality in injured patients. *Critical care medicine*. 2000 Apr 1;28(4):950-7.
14. Zou MX, Zhou RR, Wu WJ, Zhang NJ, Liu WE, Fan XG. The use of pleural fluid procalcitonin and C-reactive protein in the diagnosis of parapneumonic pleural effusions: a systemic review and meta-analysis. *The American journal of emergency medicine*. 2012 Nov 1;30(9):1907-14.
15. Khosla R, Khosla SG, Becker KL, Nylen ES. Pleural fluid procalcitonin to distinguish infectious from noninfectious etiologies of pleural effusions. *Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2016 May;11(5):363-
16. Davies HE, Davies RJ, Davies CW. Management of pleural infection in adults: British Thoracic Society pleural disease guideline 2010. *Thorax*. 2010 Aug 1;65(Suppl 2):ii41-53.

17. Wallenhaupt SL. Surgical management of thoracic empyema. *Journal of thoracic imaging*. 1991 Jul 1;6(3):80-8.
18. Meyer JA. Gotthard Bülow and closed water-seal drainage for empyema, 1875–1891. *The Annals of Thoracic Surgery*. 1989 Oct 1;48(4):597-9.
19. Pérez JM. The Eponymous Dr. Richard W. Light: Father of Pleural Medicine. *Archivos de bronconeumología: Organo oficial de la Sociedad Española de Neumología y Cirugía Torácica SEPAR y la Asociación Latinoamericana de Tórax (ALAT)*. 2022;58(3):203-4.
20. Hamm H, Brohan U, Bohmer R, Missmahl HP. Cholesterol in pleural effusions: a diagnostic aid. *Chest*. 1987 Aug 1;92(2):296-302.
21. Light RW, Jenkinson SG, Minh VD, George RB. Observations on pleural fluid pressures as fluid is withdrawn during thoracentesis. *American Review of Respiratory Disease*. 1980 May;121(5):799-804.
22. *Grays Anatomy*, 42th edition;. Peter L. Williams, MaryDyson.
23. *Sk jindal pulmonary and critical care medicine* 2nd edition
24. T.S.Ranganathan; *Human Anatomy*- 1998; 437.
25. *Crofton & Douglas textbook of respiratory diseases* fifth edition
26. Miserocchi G. Physiology and pathophysiology of pleural fluid turnover. *European Respiratory Journal*. 1997 Jan 1;10(1):219-25.
27. Zocchi L. Physiology and pathophysiology of pleural fluid turnover. *European Respiratory Journal*. 2002 Dec 1;20(6):1545-58.
28. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* Vol 162. pp 1023–1026, 2000Internet address: www.atsjournals.orgVolume and Cellular Content of Normal Pleural Fluid in Humans Examined by Pleural Lavage

29. Light RW. Pleural effusions. *Med Clin North Am.* 2011;95(6):1055-1070.
30. Sahn SA. Pleural effusions of extravascular origin. *Clin Chest Med.* 2006 Jun. 27(2):285-308.
31. Feller-Kopman D, Light R. Pleural disease. *N Engl J Med.* 2018;378(8):740–751.
32. Murray nadaels textbook of respiratory medicine 7th edition
33. Anthonisen NR, Martin RR. Regional lung function in pleural effusion. *American Review of Respiratory Disease.* 1977 Aug;116(2):201-7.
34. Light RW, Stansbury DW, Brown SE. The relationship between pleural pressures and changes in pulmonary function after therapeutic thoracentesis. *American Review of Respiratory Disease.* 1986 Apr;133(4):658-61.
35. Thomas R, Jenkins S, Eastwood PR, Lee YCG, Singh B. Physiology of breathlessness associated with pleural effusions. *Current Opinion in Pulmonary Medicine [Internet].* 2015Jul;21(4):338–45.
36. Light's book of pleural diseases third edition
37. Fishman's pulmonary diseases and disorders 6th edition
38. Muruganandan S, Azzopardi M, Thomas R, Fitzgerald DB, Kuok YJ, Cheah HM, Read CA, Budgeon CA, Eastwood PR, Jenkins S, Singh B. The Pleural Effusion And Symptom Evaluation (PLEASE) study of breathlessness in patients with a symptomatic pleural effusion. *European Respiratory Journal.* 2020 May 1;55(5).
39. Archit boloor textbook of clinical examination
40. Khajotia R. Respiratory clinics: mediastinal shift: a sign of significant clinical and radiological importance in diagnosis of malignant pleural effusion. *Malaysian family physician: the official journal of the Academy of Family Physicians of Malaysia.* 2012;7(1):34.

41. Radiopedia of pleural effusion
42. Karkhanis VS, Joshi JM. Pleural effusion: diagnosis, treatment, and management. Open access emergency medicine. 2012 Jun 25:31-52.
43. A New Radiologic Sign book of Subpulmonic Effusion- chest
44. Moulton JS, Moore PT, Mencini 6A. Treatment of loculated pleural effusions with transcatheter intracavitary urokinase. American Journal of Roentgenology. 1989 Nov 1;153(5):941-5.
- 45 Labrador-Descalzo S, Moreno Z. A case of vanishing tumor in a smoker elderly male. Atencion Primaria. 2022 Sep 6;54(10):102457-.
46. Havelock T, Teoh R, Laws D, Gleeson F. Pleural procedures and thoracic ultrasound: British Thoracic Society pleural disease guideline 2010. Thorax. 2010 Aug 1;65(Suppl 2):i61-76.
47. Chest sonography textbook by gebhard mathis
48. Hassan M, Mercer RM, Rahman NM. Thoracic ultrasound in the modern management of pleural disease. European Respiratory Review. 2020 Jun 30;29(156).
49. Soni NJ, Franco R, Velez MI, Schnobrich D, Dancel R, Restrepo MI, Mayo PH. Ultrasound in the diagnosis and management of pleural effusions. Journal of hospital medicine. 2015 Dec;10(12):811-6.
50. Balik M, Plasil P, Waldauf P, Pazout J, Fric M, Otahal M, Pachl J. Ultrasound estimation of volume of pleural fluid in mechanically ventilated patients. Intensive care medicine. 2006 Feb
51. Roch A, Bojan M, Michelet P, Romain F, Bregeon F, Papazian L, Auffray JP. Usefulness of ultrasonography in predicting pleural effusions > 500 mL in patients receiving mechanical ventilation. Chest. 2005 Jan;127(1):224-32. doi: 10.1378/chest.127.1.224. PMID: 15653988.
52. Vignon P, Chastagner C, Berkane V, Chardac E, François B, Normand S, Bonnivard M, Clavel M, Pichon N, Preux PM, Maubon A, Gastinne H. Quantitative assessment of pleural effusion in

critically ill patients by means of ultrasonography. *Crit Care Med.* 2005 Aug;33(8):1757-63. doi: 10.1097/01.ccm.0000171532.02639.08. PMID: 16096453.

53. Ibitoye BO, Idowu BM, Ogunrombi AB, Afolabi BI. Ultrasonographic quantification of pleural effusion: comparison of four formulae. *Ultrasonography.* 2018 Jul;37(3):254-260. doi: 10.14366/usg.17050. Epub 2017 Oct 18. PMID: 29228764; PMCID: PMC6044225.

54. Yataco JC, Dweik RA. Pleural effusions: evaluation and management. *Cleveland clinic journal of medicine.* 2005 Oct 1;72(10):854.

55. Algin O, Gökalp G, Topal U. Signs in chest imaging. *Diagnostic and interventional radiology.* 2011 Mar 1;17(1):18.

56. Heelan RT, Rusch VW, Begg CB, Panicek DM, Caravelli JF, Eisen C. Staging of malignant pleural mesothelioma: comparison of CT and MR imaging. *AJR. American journal of roentgenology.* 1999 Apr;172(4):1039-47.

57. Hutchinson book of clinical examination

58. Hooper C, Lee YG, Maskell N. Investigation of a unilateral pleural effusion in adults: British Thoracic Society pleural disease guideline 2010. *Thorax.* 2010 Aug 1;65(Suppl 2):ii4-17.

59. Daniel TM. Diagnostic thoracoscopy for pleural disease. *The Annals of thoracic surgery.* 1993 Sep 1;56(3):639-40.

60. BTS guidelines mark Robert- 2023

61. Valdés L, Pose A, Suárez J, Gonzalez-Juanatey JR, Sarandeses A, San José E, Dobaña JM, Salgueiro M, Suárez JR. Cholesterol: a useful parameter for distinguishing between pleural exudates and transudates. *Chest.* 1991 May 1;99(5):1097-102.

62. Sahn SA. Pleural fluid analysis: narrowing the differential diagnosis. In *Seminars in Respiratory Medicine* 1987 Jul (Vol. 9, No. 01, pp. 22-29). Copyright© 1987 by Thieme Medical Publishers,

63. Hooper C, Lee YG, Maskell N. Investigation of a unilateral pleural effusion in adults: British Thoracic Society pleural disease guideline 2010. *Thorax*. 2010 Aug 1;65(Suppl 2):ii4-17.
64. Textbook of survival guidelines by dr Akhil paul
65. Sahn SA. Pathogenesis and clinical features of diseases associated with a low pleural fluid glucose. *The pleural in health and disease*. New York: Marcel Dekker. 1985:267-85.
66. Light RW, MacGregor MI, Ball Jr WC, Luchsinger PC. Diagnostic significance of pleural fluid pH and PCO₂. *Chest*. 1973 Nov 1;64(5):591-6.
67. Roberts ME, Rahman NM, Maskell NA, Bibby AC, Blyth KG, Corcoran JP, Edey A, Evison M, de Fonseka D, Hallifax R, Harden S. British Thoracic Society guideline for pleural disease. *Thorax*. 2023 Jul 1;78(Suppl 3):s1-42.
68. Light RW, Erozan YS, Ball WC. Cells in pleural fluid: their value in differential diagnosis. *Archives of internal medicine*. 1973 Dec 1;132(6):854-60.
69. Meisel S, Shamiss A, Thaler M, Nussinovitch N, Rosenthal T. Pleural fluid to serum bilirubin concentration ratio for the separation of transudates from exudates. *Chest*. 1990 Jul 1;98(1):141-4.
70. Baba K, Hoosen AA, Langeland N, Dyrhol-Riise AM. Adenosine deaminase activity is a sensitive marker for the diagnosis of tuberculous pleuritis in patients with very low CD4 counts. *PLoS one*. 2008 Jul 30;3(7):e2788.
71. Chung JH, Kim YS, Kim SI, Park K, Park MS, Kim YS, Kim SK, Chang J, Kim SK. The diagnostic value of the adenosine deaminase activity in the pleural fluid of renal transplant patients with tuberculous pleural effusion. *Yonsei medical journal*. 2004 Aug;45(4):661-4.
72. Valdés L, San José E, Alvarez D, Sarandeses A, Pose A, Chomón B, Alvarez-Dobaño JM, Salgueiro M, Suárez JR. Diagnosis of tuberculous pleurisy using the biologic parameters adenosine deaminase, lysozyme, and interferon gamma. *Chest*. 1993 Feb 1;103(2):458-65.

73. Ocana I, Ribera E, Martinez-Vazquez JM, Ruiz I, Bejarano E, Pigrau C, Pahissa A. Adenosine deaminase activity in rheumatoid pleural effusion. *Annals of the rheumatic diseases*. 1988 May 1;47(5):394-7.
74. Burgess LJ, Maritz FJ, Le Roux I, Taljaard JF. Combined use of pleural adenosine deaminase with lymphocyte/neutrophil ratio: increased specificity for the diagnosis of tuberculous pleuritis. *Chest*. 1996 Feb 1;109(2):414-9.
75. Pérez-Rodríguez E, Castro DJ. The use of adenosine deaminase and adenosine deaminase isoenzymes in the diagnosis of tuberculous pleuritis. *Current opinion in pulmonary medicine*. 2000 Jul 1;6(4):259-66.
76. Thoracentesis for the Diagnosis and Management of Pleural Effusions: The Current State of a Centuries-Old Procedure by michelal nikolson
77. Meynaar IA, Droog W, Batstra M, Vreede R, Herbrink P. In critically ill patients, serum procalcitonin is more useful in differentiating between sepsis and SIRS than CRP, Il-6, or LBP. *Critical care research and practice*. 2011;2011(1):594645.
78. Le Moullec JM, Jullienne A, Chenais J, Lasmoles F, Guliana JM, Milhaud G, Moukhtar MS. The complete sequence of human preprocalcitonin. *FEBS letters*. 1984 Feb 13;167(1):93-7.
79. Assicot M, Bohuon C, Gendrel D, Raymond J, Carsin H, Guilbaud JJ. High serum procalcitonin concentrations in patients with sepsis and infection. *The Lancet*. 1993 Feb 27;341(8844):515-8.
80. Katz SE, Sartori LF, Williams DJ. Clinical progress note: procalcitonin in the management of pediatric lower respiratory tract infection. *Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2019 Nov;14(11):688.
81. Becker KL, Snider R, Nysten ES. Procalcitonin in sepsis and systemic inflammation: a harmful biomarker and a therapeutic target. *British journal of pharmacology*. 2010 Jan;159(2):253-64.
82. Maruna P, Nedelnikova K, Gurlich R. Physiology and genetics of procalcitonin. *Physiological Research*. 2000 Apr;49:S57-62.
83. Lippi G, Sanchis-Gomar F. Procalcitonin in inflammatory bowel disease: Drawbacks and opportunities. *World journal of gastroenterology*. 2017 Dec 12;23(47):8283.

84. Linscheid P, Seboek D, Schaer DJ, Zulewski H, Keller U, Müller B. Expression and secretion of procalcitonin and calcitonin gene-related peptide by adherent monocytes and by macrophage-activated adipocytes. *Critical care medicine*. 2004 Aug 1;32(8):1715-21.
85. Linscheid P, Seboek D, Nylen ES, Langer I, Schlatter M, Becker KL, Keller U, Müller B. In vitro and in vivo calcitonin I gene expression in parenchymal cells: a novel product of human adipose tissue. *Endocrinology*. 2003 Dec 1;144(12):5578-84.
86. Lee SH, Lee EJ, Min KH, Hur GY, Lee SY, Kim JH, Shin C, Shim JJ, In KH, Kang KH, Lee SY. Procalcitonin as a diagnostic marker in differentiating parapneumonic effusion from tuberculous pleurisy or malignant effusion. *Clinical Biochemistry*. 2013 Oct 1;46(15):1484-8.
87. Becker K. Procalcitonin: how a hormone became a marker and mediator of sepsis. *Swiss medical weekly*. 2001 Oct 20;131(4142):595-602.
88. Samsudin I, Vasikaran SD. Clinical utility and measurement of procalcitonin. *The Clinical Biochemist Reviews*. 2017 Apr;38(2):59.
89. Sachse C, Dressler F, Henkel E. Increased serum procalcitonin in newborn infants without infection. *Clinical chemistry*. 1998 Jun 1;44(6):1343-4.
90. Chiesa C, Panero A, Rossi N, Stegagno M, Giusti MD, Osborn JF, Pacifico L. Reliability of procalcitonin concentrations for the diagnosis of sepsis in critically ill neonates. *Clinical infectious diseases*. 1998 Mar 1;26(3):664-72.
91. Meisner M. Procalcitonin: biochemistry and clinical diagnosis. 2010.
92. Hubl W, Krassler J, Zingler C, Pertschy A, Hentschel J, Gerhards-Reich C, Mack M, Demant T. Evaluation of a fully automated procalcitonin chemiluminescence immunoassay. *Clinical laboratory*. 2003 Jan 1;49(7-8):319-27.
93. Waterfield T, Maney JA, Lyttle MD, McKenna JP, Roland D, Corr M, Patenall B, Shields MD, Woolfall K, Fairley D, Paediatric Emergency Research in the UK and Ireland (PERUKI). Diagnostic test accuracy of point-of-care procalcitonin to diagnose serious bacterial infections in children. *BMC pediatrics*. 2020 Dec;20:1-6.
94. Evans PT, Zhang RS, Cao Y, Breslin S, Panebianco N, Baston CM, Dibardino DM. The use of thoracic ultrasound to predict transudative and exudative pleural effusion. *POCUS journal*. 2021;6(2):97.

95. McCann FJ, Chapman SJ, Yu WC, Maskell NA, Davies RJ, Lee YG. Ability of procalcitonin to discriminate infection from non-infective inflammation using two pleural disease settings. *PLoS One*. 2012 Dec 12;7(12):e49894.
96. Watanabe N, Ishii T, Kita N, Kanaji N, Nakamura H, Nanki N, Ueda Y, Tojo Y, Kadowaki N, Bando S. The usefulness of pleural fluid presepsin, C-reactive protein, and procalcitonin in distinguishing different causes of pleural effusions. *BMC pulmonary medicine*. 2018 Dec;18:1-9.
97. Wang T, Du G, Fang L, Bai Y, Liu Z, Wang L. Value of ultrasonography in determining the nature of pleural effusion: Analysis of 582 cases. *Medicine*. 2022 Aug 19;101(33):e30119.
98. Ahmed ES, Abou Bakr SM, Eid HA, Shaarawy AT, Elsayed WT. Role of ultrasonography in the diagnosis of pleural effusion. *Egyptian Journal of Bronchology*. 2017 Jun;11:120-7.
99. Helala LA, Madkour A, Osman NM, Hetta WM, Hakim IM. Role of ultrasound in the management of pleural diseases in respiratory intensive care patients. *Egyptian Journal of Bronchology*. 2015 Apr;9:79-91.
100. Ahmad V, Patel K, Lisa A, Chua J, Ahmad S. Utilizing ultrasound to predict pleural effusion etiology. *Chest*. 2020 Oct 1;158(4):A1392.
101. Akkurt B, Kiral NG, Fidan A, Koç H, Salepci BM, Cömert SŞ. The Role of Pleural Fluid Procalcitonin in the Differential Diagnosis of Parapneumonic Pleural Effusions and its Relation with Pleural Fluid Ultrasound. *Southern Clinics of Istanbul Eurasia*. 2020;31(2):107.
102. Al-Aarag AH, Mohammed SA, Ibrahim HY, Mohammad OI. Diagnostic value of procalcitonin in pleural effusion. *The Egyptian Journal of Chest Diseases and Tuberculosis*. 2020 Apr 1;69(2):392-8.
103. Wang CY, Hsiao YC, Jerng JS, Ho CC, Lai CC, Yu CJ, Hsueh PR, Yang PC. Diagnostic value of procalcitonin in pleural effusions. *European journal of clinical microbiology & infectious diseases*. 2011 Mar;30:313-8.

104. Bandaru RC, Rachegowda N. Efficacy Of ultrasonography and computed tomography in differentiating transudate from exudate in patients with pleural effusion. *Imaging in Medicine*. 2018;10(10.14303).
105. Ahmed MI, Debbarma T, Peldon T, Debbarma B. Role Of Ultrasonography And Computed Tomography In Differentiating Transudative From Exudative Pleural Effusion.
106. El Wahsh RA, El-Habashy MM, Saad RA, Mahrous AH. Role of chest ultrasound in management of exudative pleural effusion. *International Journal of Health Sciences*. 2022(VI):143-59.
107. Yang W, Zhang B, Zhang ZM. Infectious pleural effusion status and treatment progress. *Journal of thoracic disease*. 2017 Nov;9(11):4690.
108. Brogi E, Gargani L, Bignami E, Barbariol F, Marra A, Forfori F, Vetrugno L. Thoracic ultrasound for pleural effusion in the intensive care unit: a narrative review from diagnosis to treatment. *Critical Care*. 2017 Dec;21:1-1.
109. Kim HJ, Lee HJ, Kwon SY, Yoon HI, Chung HS, Lee CT, Han SK, Shim YS, Yim JJ. The prevalence of pulmonary parenchymal tuberculosis in patients with tuberculous pleuritis. *Chest*. 2006 May 1;129(5):1253-8.
110. Na MJ. Diagnostic tools of pleural effusion. *Tuberculosis and respiratory diseases*. 2014 May;76(5):199.
111. Porcel JM, Vives M, Cao G, Bielsa S, Ruiz-González A, Martínez-Iribarren A, Esquerda A. Biomarkers of infection for the differential diagnosis of pleural effusions. *European Respiratory Journal*. 2009 Dec 1;34(6):1383-9.
112. Bandaru RC, Rachegowda N. Efficacy Of ultrasonography and computed tomography in differentiating transudate from exudate in patients with pleural effusion. *Imaging in Medicine*. 2018;10(10.14303).

113. Koçer BC, Çİledağ AY, Işık ME, Yılmaz A, Güven SF, Yüksel CA, Poyraz B, Rad AY, Kutlay HA, ÇelİK GÖ, Kaya AK. The role of pleural fluid procalcitonin level in the diagnosis of parapneumonic pleural effusion.
114. El-Shimy WS, Attia GA, Hazzaa SM, Mansour YM, Abd El-Halim WM. Diagnostic value of procalcitonin and C-reactive protein in differentiation between some benign and malignant pleural effusions. *Egyptian Journal of Chest Diseases and Tuberculosis*. 2014 Oct 1;63(4):923-30.
115. Shankar S, Gulati M, Kang M, Gupta S, Suri S. Image-guided percutaneous drainage of thoracic empyema: can sonography predict the outcome?. *European radiology*. 2000 Feb;10:495-9.
116. Chen KY, Liaw YS, Wang HC, Luh KT, Yang PC. Sonographic septation: a useful prognostic indicator of acute thoracic empyema. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*. 2000 Dec;19(12):837-43.
117. Silverman S, Mueller PR, Saini S, Hahn PF, Simeone JF, Forman BH, Steiner E, Ferrucci JT. Thoracic empyema: management with image-guided catheter drainage. *Radiology*. 1988 Oct;169(1):5-9.
118. Sharma A, Agrawal A, Sindhwani G, Sharma A, Tomo S, Charan J, Yadav D, Sharma P. Efficacy of procalcitonin and pentraxin-3 as early biomarkers for differential diagnosis of pleural effusions. *Pleura Peritoneum*. 2021 Apr 19;6(2):83-90. doi: 10.1515/pp-2021-0111. PMID: 34179342; PMCID: PMC8216840.

ANNEXURE I

BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956

Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 734/2022-23

30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "Assessment of pleural effusion using light's criteria & its correlation with ultrasound thorax and its impact on management of pleural effusion and its correlation with pleural fluid Procalcitonin levels".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr.Bokka Likhita.

NAME OF THE GUIDE Dr.Ramesh S. Babar, Professor & HoD, Dept. of Respiratory Medicine

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)

Dr. Akram A. Naikwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutination

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.

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ANNEXURE II

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

BLDEDU'S SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH

CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA, KARNATAKA - 586103

TITLE OF THE PROJECT - ASSESSMENT OF PLEURAL EFFUSION USING LIGHTS CRITERIA AND ITS CORRELATION WITH ULTRASOUND THORAX AND ITS IMPACT ON MANAGEMENT OF PLEURAL EFFUSION AND ITS CORRELATION WITH PLEURAL FLUID PROCALCITONIN LEVELS

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR - Dr. LIKHITHA. B
Department of Respiratory medicine

P.G. GUIDE NAME - DR. KEERTIVARDHAN D KULKARNI
Professor & hod of respiratory medicine

CHAIRMAN ETHICAL COMMITTEE

All aspects of this consent form are explained to the patient in the language understood by him/her.

1) PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed that the purpose of the study. I have also been given a free choice of participation in this study.

2) PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked a series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment to help the investigator in this study.

3) RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

4) BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help patients' survival and better outcome.

5) CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of Hospital records and will be subject to confidentiality and privacy regulation. Information of a sensitive personal nature

will not be a part of the medical records but will be stored in the investigator's research file and identified only by a code number. The code-key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate location. If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or teaching purposes, no name will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or videotapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photographs and videotapes and hear the audiotapes before giving this permission.

6) REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time. Dr. LIKHITHA.B is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the study, which might influence my continued participation. If during the study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. I will be given a copy of this consent form to keep for careful reading.

7) REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital. I also understand that Dr. LIKHITHA.B may

terminate my participation in the study after he has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my physician or physical therapist if this is appropriate.

8) INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study I am not waiving any of my legal rights. I have explained the purpose of the research, the procedures required, and the possible risks and benefits to the best of my ability in the patient's language.

DR. KEERTIVARDHAN D KULKARNI
(Guide)

DR. LIKHITHA. B
(Investigator)

Date:

II) STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I confirm that DR. LIKHITHA. B has explained to me the purpose of the research, the study procedures that I will undergo, and the possible risks and discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my language. I have read and understand this consent form. Therefore, I agree to give consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

Participant / Guardian

Date:

Witness to signature

Date:

ANNEXURE III

PROFORMA

Informant :

Name: CASE NO

Age: IP NO:

Sex: DOA:

Religion: DOD:

Occupation::

Residence:

Chief complaints:

History of present illness:

Past History:

Personal History:

Family History:

General Physical Examination

Built :

Height:

Weight:

Body Mass Index:

Vitals

PR:

BP:

RR:

Temp

Pallor

Cyanosis

Clubbing

Icterus

Lymphadenopathy

Edema

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

RESPIRATORY SYSTEM:

CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM:

ABDOMEN EXAMINATION:

CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM :

INVESTIGATIONS

1. CHEST XRAY PAVIEW
2. USG THORAX
3. PLEURAL FLUID ANALYSIS

ULTRASOUND THORAX	CONSERVATIVE MANAGEMENT THERAPEUTIC PLEURAL ASPIRATION	SURGICAL MANAGEMENT ICD TUBE INSERTION UNDERWATER SEAL	SURGICAL MANAGEMENT THORACOTOMY/ VATS DECORTICATIONS
Massive effusion with no septations and loculation		Yes	
Moderate effusion with no septations and loculations	Yes		
Minimal Effusion	Yes		
Effusion with internal echoes		Yes	
Effusion with thin internal septations		Yes +/- intrapleural fibrinolytic agent	
Effusion with thick internal septations			Yes
Effusion with a single locule		Yes	
Effusion with multiple locules			Yes

ULTRASOUND PATTERN AND NATURE OF EFFUSION

PATTERN	TRANSUDATIVE	EXUDATIVE
ANECHOGENIC	Yes	Yes
ECHOGENIC		Yes
COMPLEX NON SEPTATED	Yes	Yes
COMPLEX SEPTATED		Yes

THICKENED PLEURA AND ASSOCIATED PARENCHYMAL LESIONS		Yes
--	--	-----

PLEURAL FLUID ANALYSIS

CELL TYPE-

CELL COUNT-

BODY FLUIDS FOR MALIGNANCY-

GRAM STAIN-

ZN STAIN-

AEROBIC CULTURE AND SENSITIVITY-

CBNAAT FOR TB-

SUGAR-

PROTEIN-

CHLORIDE-

LDH-

ADA

PLEURAL FLUID PROCALCITONIN LEVELS:

CONCLUSION:

Date:-

Signature:-

ANNEXURE IV MASTERCHART

ETHNOLOGY	SITE	CELLO CELLTYPE	PREDON COLOR	APPEARANCE	MALIGNANCY	GRAM STAIN	ZN STAIN	AEROBIC CULTURE	SUBSTRATE	PROTEOLYTIC	LDH-F	LDH-A	S.D.M.I.	S.P.R.T.	C.M.I.A.	QUANTITY	USG FINDINGS	THICK PREP	PLEU SEPTATIONS	LIGHTS COBT	Procalcitonin	Procalcitonin	
																					ng/ml	ng/ml	
1	ETB	Left	1511 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	23	4.5	108	1007	72	228	6.3	Negative moderate	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	ICD insertion	0.34674444	345.00
2	CLD	Right	30 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	18	2.7	109	100	15.3	209	7.2	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.31481858	315.46
3	Enryema	Right	23000 Neutrophilic	Pale yellow turbid	Negative	Few pus cells seen	negative	ameobococcus pneumoniae	20	2.6	180	2034	35.3	346	6.2	Negative moderate	complex septate	Present	thick	Eudative	VATS/Thoracoscopy	0.24092024	240.92
4	CLD	Right	518 Lymphocytic	Dark yellow cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	12	2.2	101	87	118	153	5.6	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.30707443	307.07
5	CLD	Right	39 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	Few pus cells seen	negative	sterile	125	2	117	70	0.2	120	6.3	Negative moderate	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Transudative	ICD insertion	0.30826523	308.26
6	CHD	Bilateral	280 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	43	2	111	31	18.2	202	5.6	Negative mild	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.31524453	315.24
7	HF	Right	100 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	46	2	95	36	3.3	233	5.3	Negative mild	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.31964451	319.64
8	HF	Right	120 Neutrophilic	Dark yellow cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	95	3.2	132	65	8.5	458	6.8	Negative moderate	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Transudative	ICD insertion	0.31853111	318.51
9	HF	Right	525 Neutrophilic	Reddish turbid	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	83	2.4	97	89	12.3	209	5.4	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.308950489	308.91
10	CLD	Right	250 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	161	2	101	65	6.5	286	4.2	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.31174401	311.74
11	FE	Left	5950 Lymphocytic	Dark yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	80	4.4	100	160	15.8	147	6.5	Negative moderate	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32440003	324.4
12	CLD	Left	1000 Lymphocytic	Reddish turbid	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	97	3.3	100	93	11.1	173	6.7	Negative moderate	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Transudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32384088	323.86
13	FE	Left	483 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	100	4.4	100	160	15.8	147	6.5	Negative moderate	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32440003	324.4
14	CHD	Bilateral	483 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	133	2.7	103	18	10.8	383	5.8	Negative moderate	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.30550071	305.51
15	HF	Right	187 Lymphocytic	Hemorrhagic clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	284	2	101	907	8.2	207	4.9	Negative Gross	homogenous echo	Absent	nl	Transudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32006832	320.06
16	HF	Right	3292 Lymphocytic	Hemorrhagic clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	93	5.7	96	687	87.8	207	7.2	Negative moderate	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32624288	326.25
17	ETB	Left	1393 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	44	4.1	106	148	7.2	420	7.9	Negative moderate	complex septate	Absent	thick	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.31857493	318.57
18	ETB	Right	1200 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	32	4.5	101	341	67.7	51	4.5	Negative moderate	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32437278	324.37
19	CHD	Bilateral	115 Lymphocytic	Reddish cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	92	2	182	226	22	259	5.9	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32328734	323.24
20	CLD	Bilateral	338 Lymphocytic	Yellowish cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	66	4.4	94	308	5.3	233	6.2	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.32361001	323.61
21	CLD	Bilateral	188 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	134	2	20	18	2.2	234	4.8	Negative Gross	complex septate	Absent	thick	Transudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32419131	324.19
22	HF	Right	107 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	70	2.4	101	202	6.9	402	5.6	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.32564451	325.64
23	Paapneumon	Left	35271 Neutrophilic	Reddish turbid	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	31	4.3	107	187	18.4	236	3.8	Negative moderate	complex septate	Absent	thick	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32557411	325.74
24	ETB	Right	7030 Lymphocytic	Dark yellow turbid	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	56	5.5	104	603	55.6	204	7.4	Negative moderate	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.31076782	310.78
25	ETB	Left	3890 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	54	5.8	106	192	18	356	6.2	Negative moderate	complex septate	Absent	thick	Eudative	VATS/Thoracoscopy	0.32651638	326.51
26	HF	Right	30 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	73	2	108	78	4.02	81	5.2	Negative moderate	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.31164441	311.66
27	Malignancy	Right	400 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	positive	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	60	4.5	98	127	10.3	143	6.1	Negative moderate	complex septate	Absent	thick	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32811658	328.11
28	Enryema	Right	47650 Neutrophilic	Reddish turbid	Negative	Few pus cells seen	negative	sterile	20	3	139	1502	34	131	3.8	Negative moderate	complex septate	Present	thick	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32553362	325.53
29	Malignancy	Left	2010 Neutrophilic	Hemorrhagic turbid	positive	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	20	3	98	887	12.4	243	6.2	Negative mild	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.61787123	617.88
30	HF	Right	253 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	Few pus cells seen	negative	sterile	365	2.1	94	48	10.1	162	4.2	Negative moderate	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.32651641	326.51
31	ETB	Right	743 Lymphocytic	Reddish cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	52	5	100	447	40	312	6.2	Negative mild	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.61857407	618.57
32	Malignancy	Right	311 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	34	4.2	93	148	12.1	80	6.1	Negative mild	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.65522411	655.24
33	Paapneumon	Left	516 Neutrophilic	Pale yellow cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	53	4.7	99	444	35	133	7.1	Negative moderate	complex septate	Absent	thick	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32651641	326.51
34	ETB	Right	160 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	78	4.4	94	194	416	117	5.7	Negative moderate	complex septate	Absent	thick	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.44415526	444.14
35	CHD	Bilateral	245 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	84	3.8	93	193	46.2	204	4.5	Negative moderate	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.33315538	333.15
36	ETB	Right	346 Neutrophilic	Reddish cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	positive	sterile	39	2.6	96	117	55.2	174	4.7	Negative moderate	complex septate	Absent	thick	Eudative	ICD tube insertion	0.38730734	387.3
37	ETB	Right	370 Neutrophilic	Hemorrhagic	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	40	4	112	309	42	308	4.5	Negative mild	homogenous echo	Absent	nl	Eudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.32651638	326.51
38	HF	Left	693 Lymphocytic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	62	2.5	108	90	6.2	660	6.2	Negative mild	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.32651638	326.51
39	Paapneumon	Right	1653 Neutrophilic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	gram positive cocci in pairs	negative	sterile	20	3.5	94	162	128.1	327	4.7	Negative moderate	complex septate	Present	thick	Eudative	VATS/Thoracoscopy	0.32417426	324.17
40	CHD	Left	620 Neutrophilic	Pale yellow clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	71	2	101	83	6.7	1450	6.2	Negative Gross	complex nonseptate	Absent	nl	Transudative	ICD tube insertion	0.32118887	321.89
41	CLD	Right	182 Lymphocytic	Reddish clear	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	64	2.8	104	110	23.6	240	5.5	Negative Gross	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.32302452	323.02
42	HF	Right	482 Neutrophilic	Pale yellow cloudy	Negative	No organisms seen	negative	sterile	62	2	108	105	12.1	366	4.4	Negative moderate	anechogenic	Absent	nl	Transudative	Therapeutic pleural aspirate	0.32648001	326.48

ANNEXURE V

PLAGIARISM

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